

1 In silico QT and APD Prolongation Assay for Early 2 Screening of Drug-Induced Proarrhythmic Risk

3 *Lucia Romero^{a‡}, Jordi Cano^{a‡}, Julio Gomis-Tena^a, Beatriz Trenor^a, Ferran Sanz^b, Manuel*
4 *Pastor^b, Javier Saiz^{a*}*

5 ^a Centro de Investigación e Innovación en Bioingeniería (CI²B), Universitat Politècnica de
6 València, camino de Vera, s/n, 46022, Valencia, Spain.

7 ^b Research Programme on Biomedical Informatics (GRIB), Institut Hospital del Mar
8 d'Investigacions Mèdiques (IMIM), Dept. of Experimental and Health Sciences, Universitat
9 Pompeu Fabra, carrer del Dr. Aiguader, 88, 08002, Barcelona, Spain.

10 *Corresponding Author, e-mail: jsaiz@ci2b.upv.es

11

12 ABSTRACT

13 Drug-induced proarrhythmicity is a major concern for regulators and pharmaceutical companies.
14 For novel drug candidates, the standard assessment involves the evaluation of the potassium hERG
15 channels block and the in vivo prolongation of the QT interval. However, this method is known to
16 be too restrictive and to stop the development of potentially valuable therapeutic drugs. The aim
17 of this work is to create an in silico tool for early detection of drug-induced proarrhythmic risk.
18 The system is based on simulations of how different compounds affect the action potential duration

1 (APD) of isolated endocardial, midmyocardial, and epicardial cells, as well as the QT prolongation
2 in a virtual tissue. Multiple channel-drug interactions and state-of-the-art human ventricular action
3 potential models (O’Hara et al.) were used in our simulations. Specifically, 206.766 cellular and
4 7072 tissue simulations were performed by blocking the slow and the fast components of the
5 delayed rectifier current (I_{Ks} and I_{Kr} , respectively), and the L-type calcium current (I_{CaL}) at different
6 levels. The performance of our system was validated by classifying the proarrhythmic risk of 84
7 compounds, 40 of which present torsadogenic properties. Based on these results, we propose the
8 use of a new index (Tx) for discriminating torsadogenic compounds, defined as the ratio of the
9 drug concentrations producing 10% prolongation of the cellular endocardial, midmyocardial and
10 epicardial APDs and the QT interval, over the maximum effective free therapeutic plasma
11 concentration (EFTPC). Our results show that the Tx index outperforms standard methods for early
12 identification of torsadogenic compounds. Indeed, for the analyzed compounds the Tx tests
13 accuracy was in the range of 87% to 88%, compared with a 73% accuracy of the hERG IC_{50} based
14 test.

15 KEYWORDS

16 In silico, proarrhythmic risk, QT prolongation, multi-channel drugs.

17 **1. Introduction**

18 Preclinical assessment of cardiac adverse effects for drug candidates has become a priority for
19 regulatory agencies and pharmaceutical companies due to the occurrence of potentially life-
20 threatening ventricular arrhythmias following the administration of drugs¹⁻⁵. Nowadays, cardiac
21 safety test of pharmacological compounds is mainly based on the observed in vitro block of the
22 human Ether-à-go-go-Related Gene, hERG, current (encoding the pore-forming alpha-subunit of

1 the rapid component of delayed rectifier current (I_{Kr}) channels in humans) produced by the
2 compound and the *in vivo* prolongation of the QT interval (ICH S7B nonclinical guidance⁶ and
3 E14 clinical guidance⁷).

4 Indeed, many studies have revealed that block of I_{Kr} promotes the drug-induced long QT
5 syndrome, associated to increased proarrhythmic risk⁸. Prolongation of the QT interval has
6 traditionally been linked to the initiation of torsade de pointes (TdP) in the clinical practice.
7 However, there are hERG blockers that do not lead to TdP, such as verapamil^{9,10}.

8 Although current guidelines^{6,7} have been successful in preventing proarrhythmic effects of drugs,
9 the limitations of these criteria have contributed to stop the development of potentially valuable
10 compounds. A more accurate prediction of unwanted effects of drug candidates at early stages of
11 drug development is key for safety pharmacology¹¹.

12 In the last years, different modelling techniques have been employed in order to improve the
13 prediction of side effects of compounds. Biophysically detailed mathematical models of cardiac
14 electrical activity¹²⁻¹⁶ and statistical models^{9,17-19} have been used in these studies. Additionally,
15 the work of Lancaster and Sobie²⁰ combines both types of models. A nice comparison of different
16 classification schemes can be found in a recent review of Wisniowska and Polak²¹. The use of
17 modeling and simulation tools of the cardiac electrophysiological activity to predict the
18 proarrhythmic risk of drugs is currently being considered by different international initiatives, such
19 as the Comprehensive in-vitro Pro-arrhythmia Assay (CiPA)²².

20 Recent studies suggest that prediction of arrhythmogenicity could be improved by considering the
21 effects of drugs on multiple ion channels^{9,12,13,16}, the therapeutic plasma drug concentrations^{23,24},
22 and the use of biophysically detailed mathematical models of cardiac electrical activity²⁵⁻²⁹.

1 In a previous work¹³, we introduced a multiscale simulation system to predict drug-induced
2 cardiotoxicity by considering the effects of drugs in two main transmembrane ionic currents: I_{Kr}
3 and the slow component of the delayed rectifier current (I_{Ks}). Here, we create an in silico tool for
4 early detection of drug-induced proarrhythmic risk that provides a new index called Tx, which
5 summarizes in a single parameter the block of different channels in the context of the relevant drug
6 concentration. Action potential duration (APD) and QT prolongations were simulated using the
7 state of the art human ventricular action potential model (O'Hara et al. model³⁰) and taking into
8 account the effect of the block of three transmembrane ionic currents: fast and slow components
9 of the potassium delayed current (I_{Kr} and I_{Ks}) and L-type calcium current (I_{CaL}). The simulations
10 have been run over a wide range of concentrations and block values for these currents thus
11 precomputing the cardiac effect that most drugs candidates could produce.

12 The system was used to perform a retrospective cardiac safety study of 84 compounds, 40 of which
13 present torsadogenic properties, according to the information provided by CredibleMeds³¹. Our
14 results reveal that the Tx index could be a much better predictor of the torsadogenic risk than
15 criteria based solely on the concentration for 50% hERG inhibition (hERG IC_{50}). Therefore,
16 assessment of drug-induced proarrhythmicity of a compound could be improved by using the Tx
17 index based on in silico APD and QT prolongation methods. Indeed, knowing the IC_{50} s for I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} ,
18 and I_{CaL} of a compound, our method can be applied to obtain an estimate of the maximum safe
19 plasma free concentration.

20 **2. Methods**

21 *2.1. Cellular and tissue in silico simulations*

1 The action potential (AP) of human ventricular cells was simulated using the human ventricular
2 AP model proposed by O'Hara et al. (ORd³⁰). The block of I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , and I_{CaL} provoked by a drug
3 concentration (D) on the ionic current (i) was simulated by including the fraction of unblocked
4 channels ($1 - b_i$) in their formulations, and was calculated using the standard sigmoid dose-
5 response curve (Eq. 1), parameterized using the half-maximal response dose for each current
6 ($IC_{50,i}$) and considering a Hill coefficient of 1, as in previous studies^{12,13,16,20}:

$$\frac{I_i(D)}{I_i} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{D}{IC_{50,i}}} = 1 - b_i \quad (1)$$

7

8 The effects of drugs on I_{Kr} (hERG), I_{Ks} (KCNQ1), and I_{CaL} (Cav1.2) currents have been analyzed
9 in previous simulation studies using this simple pore block model^{11-13, 19, 32, 33}. APDs were sampled
10 at 90% repolarization (APD_{90}) in isolated epicardial, midmyocardial, and endocardial myocytes at
11 1 Hz, while pseudo-ECGs were computed using a one-dimensional (1D) tissue model of a
12 transmural wedge preparation. The 1D model was composed by 60 endocardial cells, 45
13 midmyocardial cells, and 60 epicardial cells³⁰ (100 μ m long each cell), as defined in ORd model.
14 Models were paced at 1 Hz, as this frequency is widely used in simulations of the human cardiac
15 electrical activity performed to predict the proarrhythmic risk of drugs^{12,16,20,28,34}. The stimulation
16 train of square transmembrane current pulses of 0.5 ms duration and 1.5-fold the diastolic threshold
17 was delivered at the isolated cells and at the endocardial end of the 1D model. The propagation of
18 the AP was described by the following nonlinear reaction diffusion equation (Eq. 2):

$$C_m \frac{\partial V_m(x, t)}{\partial t} + \sum I_{ion} + \frac{a}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{1}{R_i(x)} \frac{\partial V_m(x, t)}{\partial x} \right) = 0 \quad (2)$$

1 Where C_m is the membrane capacitance, a stands for the radius of the fiber, $\sum I_{ion}$ represents the
2 sum of all the ionic currents flowing through the cellular membrane and R_i is the intracellular
3 resistivity.

4 Isolated epicardial, midmyocardial, and endocardial cellular models were paced with 1000 pulses
5 at 1 Hz in order to achieve the steady state in control. The steady state of the 1D model in control
6 conditions was reached by applying a train of 100 pulses at 1 Hz, the initial conditions for each
7 cell type being the steady state variables obtained from the previously stabilized isolated cellular
8 models. To reach the steady state under drug exposure, the fraction of unblocked channels was
9 introduced in the models and they were paced for 100 additional pulses (1 Hz). For both, cellular
10 and 1D models, the results used in our study correspond to the 100th pulse of the last stimulation
11 period.

12 The QT interval in the pseudo-ECG was computed as the interval between the onset of the QRS
13 complex and the point where the end of the T wave reached the baseline. The pseudo-ECG was
14 measured at 2 cm from the epicardial end. 15 cells from both ends of the fiber were excluded from
15 the gradient measurement to eliminate boundary effects.³⁰

16 2.2. Drug dataset

17 The proarrhythmic risk of 84 compounds (see Table 1) was assessed using our in silico APD₉₀ and
18 QT prolongation assays. For these drugs, clinical human torsadogenic risk classification was taken
19 from CredibleMeds, which is the current AZCERT's website³¹, defining the following categories:
20 Class 1, compounds with risk of TdP; Class 2, compounds with possible risk of TdP; Class 3,

1 compounds with conditional risk of TdP; and Class 4, drugs that should be avoided by patients
2 with congenital LQTS. We defined the 40 Class 1 and 2 compounds as torsadogenic due to their
3 ability to produce TdP on their own, while the 44 Class 3 and 4 compounds were defined as non-
4 torsadogenic as they require specific interactions to produce TdP. According to Mirams et al.¹²,
5 ajmaline was included in Class 1. Drugs for which no evidence of TdP was found in Crediblemeds
6 were also included in Class 4. IC₅₀ values for I_{Kr}, I_{Ks}, and I_{CaL} and EFTPC values were obtained
7 from public databases, like DailyMed, PubChem, and DrugBank, when available. Otherwise, the
8 values were taken from the scientific literature. EFTPC values were used either directly from the
9 source or calculated from peak plasma concentrations derived from the administration of the drug
10 alone (see Supporting Information, Table S1). We consistently selected the worst-case scenario by
11 searching for the highest dosage regimen proposed by the labels. IC₅₀ values registered in
12 mammalian tissues have been selected when available, avoiding those extracted from *Xenopus*
13 oocytes. Median values were used when multiple IC₅₀ values were presented. Dashed IC₅₀ boxes
14 mean that no value was found in public databases neither in the scientific literature for these
15 compounds. In those cases, our simulations assume no block of the corresponding channel.

Compound Name	Class	pIC ₅₀			EFTPC (nM)	Compound Name	Class	pIC ₅₀			EFTPC (nM)
		hERG	I _{Ks}	I _{CaL}				hERG	I _{Ks}	I _{CaL}	
Ajmaline	1	5.98	-	-	1500	Metronidazole	3	2.87	-	3.75	210336
Amiodarone	1	6.38	5.59	6.57	63.5	Nelfinavir	3	4.90	4.10	-	60.25
Astemizole	1	8.22	-	5.98	0.3	Paroxetine	3	5.72	-	5.41	12.7
Bepridil	1	7.16	5.10	6.08	33	Quetiapine	3	5.42	-	4.98	461.9
Chlorpromazine	1	5.81	3.00	4.15	66.4	Ranolazine	3	4.90	2.72	3.51	2311
Cilostazol	1	4.86	-	4.04	162.4	Solifenacin	3	6.60	4.50	5.20	3.47
Cisapride	1	7.68	5.47	4.56	4.9	Voriconazole	3	3.31	-	3.38	5699
Clarithromycin	1	4.06	-	-	4011	Alvimopan	4	3.10	4.30	5.30	5.17
Disopyramide	1	5.00	4.09	4.96	4713	Ambrisentan	4	3.30	3.30	2.60	75.3
Dofetilide	1	7.75	-	-	2	Ceftriaxone	4	3.35	-	3.81	13704
Domperidone	1	6.88	-	-	5.79	Darifenacin	4	7.10	4.70	2.80	0.27
Donepezil	1	6.16	-	4.47	6.56	Darunavir	4	3.80	3.50	-	862.5
Dronedarone	1	7.29	5.00	6.75	0.79	Deferasirox	4	2.40	-	3.00	1403
Droperidol	1	7.22	-	5.12	16	Desvenlafaxine	4	3.60	-	-	3901
Flecainide	1	5.82	-	4.57	1448	Diazepam	4	4.27	-	4.52	29
Halofantrine	1	6.42	-	5.72	172	Diltiazem	4	4.88	-	6.12	120.6
Haloperidol	1	7.44	-	5.77	3.6	Doxorubicin	4	3.00	5.32	-	4646
Ibutilide	1	7.75	-	4.20	22	Duloxetine	4	5.42	5.00	5.55	9.22
Levofloxacin	1	3.37	-	-	30932	Ebastine	4	6.14	6.10	-	0.14
Methadone	1	5.46	-	4.43	507	Eltrombopag	4	6.20	-	-	158.9
Moxifloxacin	1	4.11	3.80	3.40	6228	Etravirine	4	3.80	2.90	-	3.38
Ondansetron	1	6.09	3.00	-	178.6	Everolimus	4	3.30	4.00	-	8.03
Procainamide	1	3.57	-	3.41	35058	Lamivudine	4	2.69	-	4.27	1446
Quinidine	1	5.90	4.36	4.81	2960	Lamotrigine	4	3.60	3.80	2.80	19083
Sotalol	1	3.29	-	-	18358	Linezolid	4	2.94	-	3.98	24856
Sparfloxacin	1	4.66	-	4.05	1766	Loratadine	4	5.22	-	4.94	0.4
Tedisamil	1	6.66	5.19	-	85	Maraviroc	4	4.40	4.20	-	415
Terfenadine	1	7.30	5.36	6.51	9	Mibefradil	4	5.77	4.93	6.29	12
Terodiline	1	6.71	4.56	4.87	11.23	Mitoxantrone	4	3.27	-	4.65	225
Thioridazine	1	6.70	4.99	5.88	979	Nebivolol	4	6.50	4.80	-	1
Clozapine	2	5.64	-	5.44	70.8	Nifedipine	4	3.87	3.44	7.28	32.3
Dasatinib	2	4.80	3.60	3.40	20.4	Nisoldipine	4	4.64	4.40	7.10	0.10
Lapatinib	2	6.00	3.60	2.70	41.8	Palonosetron	4	5.70	4.30	3.40	1.04
Nilotinib	2	6.90	3.40	3.70	60	Pentobarbital	4	2.84	3.72	3.52	5171
Oxofloxacin	2	2.85	-	-	8656	Phenytoin	4	3.83	3.00	4.66	3964
Paliperidone	2	5.90	3.60	3.40	68.9	Propranolol	4	5.09	3.00	4.71	10.1
Risperidone	2	6.63	5.01	4.14	6.96	Raltegravir	4	3.11	4.60	3.61	7001
Saquinavir	2	4.77	-	5.72	334	Ribavirin	4	3.02	-	3.21	15069
Sunitinib	2	6.60	4.20	4.10	19	Sildenafil	4	4.50	3.40	4.00	100
Tolterodine	2	7.90	4.10	-	0.39	Silodosin	4	5.10	3.60	3.10	11.2
						Sitagliptin	4	3.83	3.10	3.83	589
						S-oxybutynin	4	4.92	4.54	4.79	0.05
						Tadalafil	4	4.00	3.80	-	50.1
						Telbivudine	4	0.80	3.60	-	14731

1

2 **Table 1.** Characteristics of the 84 drugs used in this study: name (first column), torsadogenic risk

3 (second column and color-coded background of the first column: red (Class 1), orange (Class 2),

4 bright green (Class 3) and dark green (Class 4)), pIC₅₀ (-log IC₅₀) values for hERG, I_{Ks}, and I_{CaL}

5 (3rd to 5th column) and the EFTPC (6th column). References for all the values in this table are

6 given in the Supporting Information (Table S1).

7 3. Results

1 3.1 APD and QT

2 The effect of the 84 selected drugs on the endocardial, midmyocardial, and epicardial APD₉₀ was
3 simulated using the pIC₅₀ values for hERG, I_{Ks}, and I_{CaL}, and the EFTPC for each compound (see
4 all detailed results in the Supporting Information, Table S2). Figure 1 illustrates some examples
5 of the simulated APs of isolated cells (from left to right) under control conditions and in the
6 presence of bepridil ([D] = EFTPC = 33 nM) and nifedipine ([D] = EFTPC = 32.3 nM) (from top
7 to bottom). Vertical lines in each panel correspond to 10% APD₉₀ prolongation. Simulated
8 endocardial, midmyocardial, and epicardial control APD₉₀s are 266.4 ms, 330.3 ms, and 223.8 ms,
9 respectively. This figure shows that the APD₉₀ is markedly prolonged under exposure to the
10 EFTPC of the torsadogenic compound bepridil (APD₉₀s are 331.1 ms, 398.0 ms, and 278.0 ms,
11 and APD₉₀ increments are 24.3%, 20.5%, and 24.2%, respectively). On the contrary, APD₉₀ is
12 reduced under exposure to the EFTPC of the non-torsadogenic compound nifedipine (endocardial,
13 midmyocardial, and epicardial APD₉₀s are 236.6 ms, 315.7 ms, and 216.1 ms, and APD₉₀
14 increments are -11.2%, -4.4%, and -3.4%, respectively).

1

2 **Figure 1.** Simulated time course of the action potential of isolated endocardial (Endo),
 3 midmyocardial (Mid) and epicardial (Epi) cells (from left to right) under control conditions and in
 4 the presence of bepridil (33 nM) and nifedipine (32.3 nM) (from top to bottom). Vertical lines in
 5 each panel correspond to 10% prolongation of the control APD₉₀ (APD_{90CNT}). White and black
 6 rectangles correspond to the difference between the “110% APD_{90CNT}” and the APD₉₀.

7 As the QT interval prolongation is used in the assessment of drug proarrhythmic risks, the effects
 8 of the 84 compounds on the QT interval was also simulated (see Supporting Information, Table
 9 S2). Figure 2 depicts the virtual one-dimensional transmural tissue (top panel) and the simulated
 10 pseudo-ECG at 2 cm from the epicardial end, for control, and for bepridil and nifedipine at their
 11 respective EFTPC (second to bottom panel). Simulated control QT interval (QT_{CNT}) is 313 ms.
 12 Vertical lines in each panel correspond to 10% prolongation of the QT_{CNT}¹³. The QT interval is
 13 markedly prolonged under exposure to the EFTPC of bepridil (QT interval = 376 ms and QT
 14 interval increment = 20.1%), while it is reduced under exposure to the EFTPC of nifedipine (QT

- 1 interval = 299 ms and QT interval increment = -4.5%). The effects of these two drugs on the QT
- 2 interval are in agreement with those obtained in the APD_{90S} of isolated cells (Figure 1).

3

4 **Figure 2.** Representation of the virtual transmural 1D tissue (top panel) and the time course of the

5 pseudo-ECG for control and for bepridil and nifedipine at their therapeutic concentrations (second

6 to bottom panel), respectively. Black vertical lines in each panel correspond to 10% prolongation

7 of the control QT interval (QT_{CNT}), whose measurement is shown in red.

8 In order to facilitate the prediction of the potential proarrhythmic risk of a wide range of drugs

9 without carrying out a time-consuming simulation, the effect on the simulated action potential

10 durations of the three types of myocardial cells and of QT intervals were pre-computed for a large

1 number of I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , and I_{CaL} block values and concentration combinations. 206.766 simulations of
2 the electrical activity of isolated myocytes were run at a pacing rate of 1 Hz, varying the ratios of
3 drug concentration over the IC_{50} of each considered ion channel (I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , and I_{CaL}), ranging from
4 10^{-3} to 10^1 with a $10^{0.1}$ step increment. 7072 simulations were performed to obtain the QT intervals
5 at 1 Hz. In this case, the ratios of drug concentration over the IC_{50} ranged from 10^{-2} to 10^1 for I_{Kr}
6 and I_{Ks} and from 10^{-2} to 10^0 for I_{CaL} . Additionally, step increments depended on the ion channel.
7 Specifically, I_{Kr} step increment was set to $10^{0.2}$ except for the ratios between $10^{-1.2}$ and $10^{-0.2}$, where
8 it was set to $10^{0.1}$, and I_{Ks} and I_{CaL} step increments were set to $10^{0.25}$ and $10^{0.2}$, respectively.

9 Figure 3 shows a 3D representation of the surface (blue striped) corresponding to the 110% of
10 control APD_{90} (110% CNT) for endocardial (top left), midmyocardial (top right), and epicardial
11 (bottom left) cells, as well as the QT interval (bottom right). Coordinate axes represent the
12 logarithm of the ratio of the drug concentration (D) over the IC_{50} of each channel, which expresses
13 how much larger the concentration used in the simulation is than the concentration known to block
14 50% of channels. I_{Kr} and I_{Ks} block increases APD_{90} s and the QT interval, while I_{CaL} block decreases
15 them, so the back bottom left zones of the blue surface correspond to APD_{90} s and QT intervals
16 longer than 110% of control values while front top right zones correspond to APD_{90} s and QT
17 intervals shorter than 110% of control values. Those compounds that fall left to the 110% blue
18 surfaces prolong the APD_{90} or the QT interval more than 10%, like disopyramide (red triangle)
19 and bepridil (red cube) at EFTPC. Conversely, those compounds that fall right of the 110% blue
20 surfaces prolong the APD_{90} or QT less than 10%, like non-torsadogenic drugs, raltegravir (green
21 circle) and phenytoin (green cube), at EFTPC.

22 It is possible to observe how the surfaces representing the 110% of control of the endocardial and
23 epicardial APD_{90} and of the QT interval are quite similar, while the midmyocardial APD_{90} is more

1 sensitive to I_{Ks} block. Also, within the computed limits, I_{Kr} block exerts the strongest influence on
2 APD_{90} and QT prolongation among the three channels. Indeed, approximately 9% of I_{Kr} channels
3 ($\log([D]/IC_{50-I_{Kr}}) = -1$) should be blocked in order to reach the 110% of the endocardial APD_{90} and
4 the QT interval. However, when I_{CaL} is inhibited, the percentage of blocked I_{Kr} channels needed to
5 prolong the 10% of the APD_{90} and the QT interval increases. For example, for 50% of I_{CaL}
6 inhibition ($\log([D]/IC_{50-I_{CaL}}) = 0$), the percentage of I_{Kr} block reaches 24%, with no block of I_{Ks}
7 ($\log([D]/IC_{50-I_{Ks}}) = -3$).

1

2 **Figure 3.** 3D representation of the surface (blue striped) corresponding to the 110% of the control
 3 endocardial (top left), midmyocardial (top right), and epicardial (bottom left) APD₉₀ and QT
 4 interval (bottom right) together with selected torsadogenic drugs, namely, disopyramide (red
 5 triangle), bepridil (red cube), and non-torsadogenic drugs, namely, raltegravir (green circle) and
 6 phenytoin (green cube). Coordinate axes represent the logarithm of the ratio of the drug
 7 concentration over the IC₅₀ of each channel ($\log([D]/IC_{50})$).

8

1 3.3 New indices for TdP risk assessment

2 Figure 4 represents the relationship between the pIC_{50} hERG values ($-\log IC_{50}$ hERG) and the risk
 3 classification for the 84 drugs, 40 torsadogenic and 44 non-torsadogenic drugs (positive response
 4 $pIC_{50} > 6$). This figure shows that 39 out of the 44 non-torsadogenic compounds (Class 4 (dark
 5 green) and Class 3 (bright green) compounds) have pIC_{50} hERG values smaller than 6 (vertical
 6 black line), and their non-torsadogenic risk would be well predicted by this criterion, while 5 out
 7 of those 44 would be misclassified as positives. Conversely, 18 out of the 40 torsadogenic drugs
 8 (Class 1 (red) and Class 2 (orange)) have pIC_{50} hERG values smaller than 6, resulting in false
 9 negatives. The performance of this test is described by the confusion matrix included in Figure 4B.
 10 The performance for the decision pIC_{50} hERG > 6 was: sensitivity (true positive rate) of 55%,
 11 specificity (true negative rate) of 89%, and accuracy (true rate) of 73%.

12

13 **Figure 4.** A: Relationship between the pIC_{50} hERG values ($-\log IC_{50}$ hERG) and the color-coded
 14 risk classification for the 84 drugs used in this study: Class 1 (red) and Class 2 (orange), Class 3
 15 (bright green) and Class 4 (dark green). The vertical line corresponds to pIC_{50} hERG = 6. B:
 16 confusion matrix of the pIC_{50} hERG criterion.

1 In order to summarize the block of the different channels in the range of the relevant drug
2 concentration in a single parameter, we define the new index, Tx, as the ratio of drug
3 concentrations leading to a 10% prolongation of the APD₉₀ or QT ([D₁₀]) over the maximum
4 effective free therapeutic plasma concentration (EFTPC), which is the peak concentration of free
5 (unbound) drug in blood plasma at maximum therapeutic dose:

$$T_x = \frac{[D_{10}]}{EFTPC} \quad (3)$$

6 This index is quantified using the following method. The APD₉₀ and QT at maximum effective
7 free therapeutic concentration (D = EFTPC) of a certain compound are looked up in the pre-
8 computed matrices (see Figure 3). Then, the value of log([D]/IC₅₀) for each channel is increased
9 or reduced by 0.1 if the APD₉₀ or QT is shorter or longer than 110% of control value, respectively,
10 and the APD₉₀ or QT is evaluated at this new concentration in the matrices. These two steps are
11 repeated until the 110% of APD₉₀ or QT is reached, denoting the latter concentration as [D₁₀].
12 Finally, Tx is computed as the ratio of [D₁₀] over the maximum therapeutic concentration
13 (Tx=[D₁₀]/EFTPC). Because of the resolution of the QT matrix, if a specific value was not
14 computed, the closest available value was used instead.

15 The previously explained method was used to assign a Tx value to every drug in Table 1 (see
16 Supporting Information, Table S2). In order to select the Tx-APD values that best classify drugs
17 for torsadogenic risk, Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves were constructed. Figure 5
18 shows the ROC curves for endocardial Tx-APD_{Endo} (green), midmyocardial Tx-APD_{Mid} (black),
19 and epicardial Tx-APD_{Epi} (blue) for increasing decision thresholds and the optimal cut-off points
20 where sensitivity and specificity are maximal (arrows). This figure illustrates that the ROC curves
21 are very similar, being the area under these curves (AUC) of 0.91, 0.90 and 0.90 for the Tx-

1 APD_{Endo}, Tx-APD_{Mid}, and Tx-APD_{Epi}, respectively, which are indicative of overall concordance.
2 These indicators would therefore provide similar predictions. The optimal cut-off points of the Tx-
3 APD_{Endo}, Tx-APD_{Mid}, and Tx-APD_{Epi} were 8, 8, and 6.4, respectively. The ROC curves for the Tx-
4 APD_{Endo} were also generated at 2 and 0.5 Hz. As they are very similar to the Tx-APD_{Endo} ROC curve at
5 1Hz (see Figure S3 in the supporting information), we maintained the frequency at 1Hz.

6
7 **Figure 5.** In silico isolated cellular Tx-APD assays. ROC curves for the Tx-APD and optimal cut-
8 off points where sensitivity and specificity are maximal (arrows) for the Tx-APD_{Endo} (green), Tx-
9 APD_{Mid} (black) and Tx-APD_{Epi} (blue) (8, 8 and 6.4, respectively). The area under the curves
10 (AUC) is also indicated.

11 Figure 6A represents the obtained Tx-APD (see also Supporting Information, Table S2), each row
12 containing compounds belonging to only one CredibleMeds class. Vertical lines were drawn
13 matching the optimal cut-off values whose confusion matrices are summarized in Figure 6B. All
14 these tests led to very similar accuracies (86% - 87%). However, Tx-APD_{Endo} and Tx-APD_{Epi} led
15 to 85% sensitivity and 89% specificity, while Tx-APD_{Mid} led to 85% sensitivity and 86%
16 specificity.

1

2 **Figure 6.** In silico isolated cellular Tx-APD assays. A: Relationship between the Tx-APD_{Endo}, Tx-
 3 APD_{Mid} and Tx-APD_{Epi} (triangles, squares and circles, respectively) values and the risk
 4 classification for the drugs: Class 1 (red), Class 2 (orange), Class 3 (bright green) and Class 4
 5 (dark green). B: Confusion matrices for the Tx-APDs. The values of the true positive rate (TPR),
 6 true negative rate (TNR), and accuracy (A) are also indicated.

7 Similarly, a ROC curve was constructed to study if the index Tx-QT could improve the prediction
 8 of torsadogenic risk (Figure 7A). Figure 7B shows the relationship between the Tx-QT and the
 9 risk classification for the 84 drugs (see also Supporting Information, Table S2), which resembles
 10 the relationships between the three Tx-APDs and the risk classification for the drugs. The ROC
 11 curve for the Tx-QT shows an area under the curve of 0.90, which is also very similar to the Tx-
 12 APDs (Figure 5). The arrow represents the Tx-QT (9,2) that provided optimal overall prediction
 13 of the torsadogenic risk, with 85% sensitivity, 89% specificity and 87% accuracy (see confusion
 14 matrix in Figure 7C).

1

2 **Figure 7.** In silico QT interval Tx assays. A: ROC curves for the Tx-QT and optimal cut-off points

3 where sensitivity and specificity are maximal for the Tx-QT (arrow, 9.2). The area under the curve

4 is also indicated. B: Relationship between Tx-QT and the risk classification for the drugs: Class

5 1 (red), Class 2 (orange), Class 3 (bright green) and Class 4 (dark green). C: confusion matrix for

6 the Tx-QT. The values of the true positive rates (TPR), true negative rates (TNR), and accuracies

7 (A) are also indicated.

8 Figure 8 shows the torsadogenic risk classification of the 84 compounds using three different

9 criteria: pIC50 hERG >6 (top panel), Tx-APD_{Endo}<8.0 (middle panel) and Tx-QT<9.2 (bottom

10 panel). It is worth noting that both Tx indices misclassified the same 11 compounds from the 84

11 included in the data set, whereas hERG test misclassified 23 compounds. Tx indices misclassified

12 as non-torsadogenic (false negative) 3 Class 1 compounds (compounds with risk of TdP), namely,

13 cilostazol, donepezil and dronedarone, and 3 Class 2 compounds (compounds with possible risk

14 of TdP), namely, dasatinib, ofloxacin and saquinavir. Additionally, Tx indices also misclassified

15 as torsadogenic (false positive) 3 Class 3 compounds (compounds with conditional risk of TdP),

- 1 namely, metronidazole, quetiapine and ranolazine, and 2 Class 4 compounds, namely, eltrombopag and lamotrigine.
- 2 and lamotrigine.

- 3
- 4 **Figure 8.** Torsadogenic risk classification of the 84 compounds using: pIC₅₀ hERG > 6 (top panel),
- 5 Tx-Endo < 8.0 (middle panel) and Tx-QT < 9.2 (bottom panel).

1 The predictive power of the Tx indices was assessed by using a leave-one-out cross-validation
2 procedure. We built 84 different datasets (training sets) by removing one drug from the total
3 compounds each time. ROC curves for the 84 training sets were used to estimate the optimal cut-
4 off Tx of each training sets (not shown). ROC curves for APD of endocardial, midmyocardial, and
5 epicardial cells and for QT interval present very consistent values, with a cut-off Tx of 7.91 ± 0.32
6 (mean \pm SD), 6.33 ± 0.18 , 6.31 ± 0.00 and 9.10 ± 0.19 , a sensitivity of 0.85 ± 0.01 , 0.83 ± 0.01 , 0.85 ± 0.01
7 and 0.85 ± 0.01 , a specificity of 0.89 ± 0.01 , 0.89 ± 0.01 , 0.89 ± 0.01 and 0.89 ± 0.01 , and an area under
8 the curve (AUC) of 0.91, 0.90, 0.90 and 0.90, respectively. For each training set, the “left-out”
9 drug was classified according to its Tx value. At the end of the procedure, we observed that there
10 was a group of drugs that were misclassified for any of the Tx used in each test. Tx-APD_{Endo}, Tx-
11 APD_{Mid}, and Tx-QT, also misclassified clozapine, as it is the frontier compound when selecting
12 the optimal cut-off Tx in every ROC curve. In summary, approximately 14% of the drugs are
13 misclassified when any of the Tx indices are used to predict the torsadogenic risk.

14 Figure 9 shows a 3D representation of the surface (blue striped) corresponding to optimal cut-off
15 points in ROC curves for Tx-APD_{Endo} (top left), Tx-APD_{Mid} (top right), and Tx-APD_{Epi} (bottom
16 left) APD₉₀ and Tx-QT (bottom right) together with Tx calculated for selected drugs. Tx matrices
17 were built using the same APD and QT matrices used to generate Figure 3. Tx matrices were
18 constructed to provide a ready-to-use tool for Tx assessment for drugs whose IC_{50s} for I_{Kr}, I_{Ks} and
19 I_{CaL}, as well as their target concentration, have been characterized.

1

2 **Figure 9.** 3D representation of the surface (blue striped) corresponding to optimal cut-off points
 3 in ROC curves for Tx-APD_{Endo} (top left), Tx-APD_{Mid} (top right), and Tx-APD_{Epi} (bottom left)
 4 APD₉₀ and Tx-QT (bottom right) together with Tx calculated for selected torsadogenic drugs,
 5 namely, disopyramide (red triangle), bepridil (red cube), and non-torsadogenic drugs, namely,

1 raltegravir (green circle) and phenytoin (green cube). Coordinate axes represent the logarithm of
2 the ratio of the drug concentration over the IC₅₀ of each channel ($\log([D]/IC_{50})$).

3 Matrices corresponding to Figures 3 and 9 are available from the institutional and public repository
4 of the Polytechnic University of Valencia (RIUNET, <http://hdl.handle.net/10251/90297>).
5 Moreover, these matrices were incorporated in a set of predictive models developed within the
6 framework of the eTOX project [10.3390/ijms1303382] and included in the eTOXsys integrated
7 predictive system [10.1002/minf.201400193]. The open access version of these models is made
8 accessible on-line (<http://etoxlab-lqt.upf.edu>) allowing to reproduce the results described here as
9 well as to carry out the assessment of the proarrhythmic risk for other substances. In the case of
10 new compounds, as the EFTPC is unknown, Tx matrices can be used to find an estimate of the
11 maximum safe concentration. For this purpose, an initial concentration must be provided instead
12 of the EFTPC, together with the IC₅₀s. 84 drugs, 40 torsadogenic and 44 nontorsadogenic drugs
13 This Tx value must be compared to the optimal cut-off value of the model. If it is higher, then, the
14 concentration should be increased while if it is lower, it should be decreased. Thus, to find a
15 maximum safe concentration, the process must be repeated for several concentrations until the
16 resulting Tx is equal to the optimal cut-off value of the model.

17 **4. Discussion**

18 *4.1 Main findings*

19 In this paper, we describe a new tool for the preclinical assessment torsadogenic risk that provides
20 better predictions than the current state-of-the-art methodology, based only on hERG block. The
21 torsadogenic risk assessment is based on a new index, Tx, which integrates the influence of
22 relevant factors and is defined as the ratio of the drug concentration producing 10% prolongation

1 of the cellular endocardial, midmyocardial, and epicardial APDs or the QT interval over the
2 maximum EFTPC. This tool employs a large number of values of prolongations of the APD₉₀ and
3 QT interval caused by the multi-channel block of three important ionic membrane currents (I_{Kr} ,
4 I_{Ks} , and I_{CaL}), which are predicted by computer simulations of the electrophysiological activity of
5 the cardiac cells. By including these multi-channel effects and the maximum EFTPC, mis-
6 classifications in a group of 84 compounds using the hERG block criterion were drastically
7 reduced (more than 50%), from 23 to 11. In our opinion, adoption of these tools into cardiovascular
8 safety assessment could speed up and reduce the cost of cardiac safety screening in the early stages
9 of drug discovery.

10 *4.2 In silico APD₉₀ and QT prolongation assay versus the hERG block test*

11 Standard assessment methodologies focused on hERG block exhibit a poor performance^{22,35}.
12 Indeed, when applying the hERG test (positive response: hERG pIC₅₀>6) to the 84 compounds
13 considered in this work, it exhibited a sensitivity of 55%, a specificity of 89%, and an accuracy of
14 73%, which is in close agreement with previous studies^{9,36}. In comparison, the in silico Tx tests
15 described in this study presented an accuracy of 86%-87%.

16 In a previous paper, we showed that the prediction of the TdP risk obtained with the classic hERG
17 block could be improved by simulating the block of I_{Kr} and I_{Ks} using a guinea-pig AP model¹³. In
18 the same year, Mirams and coworkers simulated the block of I_{Kr} , I_{CaL} , and I_{Na} by 31 drugs with
19 different risks of TdP and observed that simulation of the human ventricular APD at therapeutic
20 concentrations improved the prediction of Redfern and coworkers¹². Both works were pioneers in
21 using computer models to introduce the multichannel effects of drugs for predicting torsadogenic
22 risks. In a posterior work, Mirams et al.¹⁶ also assessed the performance of the prediction of the

1 thorough QT assay in 34 drugs by using several ventricular human models and they showed that
2 the O'Hara et al. model³⁰ exhibited the best performance (88% accuracy, 71% sensitivity and 100%
3 specificity when considering a wider range of concentrations). More recently, Lancaster and
4 Sobie²⁰ have also evaluated arrhythmia risk using different ventricular human models and have
5 obtained better scores with the O'Hara et al. model (89.5% accuracy, 95.9% sensitivity and 81.1%
6 specificity). In that work, they combined multi-channel block simulations of 68 drugs (with a total
7 of 86 cases, as 18 of these drugs were simulated using two different models, each of them
8 constructed with the data of only one of the two sources of experimental data used in that paper)
9 with statistical analysis and machine-learning. They observed that arrhythmia risk is influenced by
10 both the action potential and the intracellular calcium concentrations waveforms.

11 The better performance of our in silico tool compared to the hERG test cannot be attributed solely
12 to the consideration of the multi-channel block, but also to the use of compound EFTPC. Indeed,
13 previous works have shown that torsadogenic risk predictions can be improved by including the
14 estimated free plasma concentration at therapeutic doses of the compound and multi-channel block
15 effects. In 2003, Redfern and coworkers observed that a safety factor of 30 of the ratio of the hERG
16 IC₅₀ over the maximum effective free therapeutic plasma concentration could provide good
17 torsadogenic risk prediction for 52 drugs²³ (77,4% accuracy, 87.5% sensitivity and 68%
18 specificity). Later, Gintant²⁴ proposed the value 45 for the safety margin, defined as the ratio of
19 the hERG IC₅₀ over the mean maximal plasma drug concentrations during thorough QT studies.
20 Our work extends their findings with a larger dataset and the inclusion of the multichannel effects
21 of the compounds.

22 All in all, our results show that Tx index is a better predictor than the hERG pIC₅₀ test (accuracy≈
23 88% compared with 73%, respectively) and that the results of predictions obtained with the four

1 Tx tests (Tx-APD_{Endo}, Tx-APD_{Mid}, and Tx-APD_{Epi} and Tx-QT) are very similar. Moreover, the
2 accuracy of our classification method (87%) is in line with the scores of the predictions of recent
3 studies, such as Mirams et al. 2014 (88%), Lancaster and Sobie 2016 (89.5%), or Kramer et al.
4 (90.9%), but our study considers a larger number of compounds (84, compared to 34, 68 and 55,
5 respectively).

6 Our simulations have shown that I_{Ks} exerts a small influence on APD₉₀ of isolated cells and QT
7 prolongation under regular conditions. This is in accordance with the small amplitude of the I_{Ks} on
8 isolated myocytes from human left ventricles³⁷ and with other simulation results^{16,30}. Moreover,
9 our results show that the role of I_{CaL} block on APD₉₀ of isolated cells and on QT prolongation is
10 relevant, although to a lesser extent than I_{Kr} block. These facts suggest that the experimental and
11 in silico study of the effects of drugs on I_{Kr} and I_{CaL} on myocytes isolated from human ventricles
12 is more relevant than drug effects on I_{Ks} . This result is in agreement with the work of Kramer and
13 collaborators who observed that the TdP risk prediction provided by the comparison of the
14 blocking potencies between I_{Kr} and I_{CaL} was drastically better than the prediction obtained by the
15 hERG assay in 55 drugs⁹ (90.9% accuracy, 96.9% sensitivity and 82.6% specificity).

16 Other works have simulated APD₉₀ changes in isolated endocardial cells of different species, such
17 as guinea pigs¹³, rabbits, dogs, and humans^{12,16}, and QT interval changes in rabbit¹⁵ to predict
18 cardiac safety of torsadogenic drugs. Beattie et al. showed that in silico simulation of the QT
19 prolongation of the rabbit left-ventricular wedge assay had a good predictive ability (78%
20 accuracy) of the experimental results of the rabbit left-ventricular wedge assay¹⁵. We selected The
21 most recent human ventricular AP model for our simulations, instead of models of other species
22 with the aim of obtaining more accurate predictions of drug proarrhythmicity risk in humans³⁸.
23 Indeed, comparison between human and other species has revealed a lack of a transient outward

1 current (I_{to}) in guinea pig, a small slow delayed rectifier current (I_{Ks}) and TdP predisposition in
2 rabbit, and a large I_{Ks} in guinea pig³⁹. Other studies have shown that human I_{Ks} differs from that
3 reported in guinea pig, and it better resembles the ventricular canine or rabbit I_{Ks} ³⁷.

4 Our work feeds from the progresses achieved by the aforementioned works, such as the
5 consideration of the therapeutic concentrations and the multi-channel effects, and the use of the
6 most recent human ventricular action potential model and goes a step further by providing a tool
7 for prediction of the torsadogenic risk that can be used by the pharmaceutical companies at the
8 early stages of drug development. This tool can be applied when the IC_{50s} for I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , and I_{CaL} of
9 a new compound are estimated without the need of high performance hardware or cardiac
10 modeling specialized staff, as the simulations have been pre-computed, allowing for an estimate
11 of a safe concentration. Moreover, the number of drugs used to depict the ROC curves is
12 significantly higher than the number of compounds used in most previous works.

13 The new Tx index has significantly reduced the misclassification obtained with hERG test,
14 although some false positive and false negative predictions with hERG tests are also misclassified
15 with our Tx index. There are many drug-related aspects that were not included in our work mainly
16 due to information unavailability, such as trafficking inhibition, the effects on other pathways, the
17 presence of metabolites and higher levels of the compound in the myocardium than in blood
18 plasma. Although these aspects can also apply to properly classified drugs, they could have favored
19 the misclassification of some drugs. For example, it has been reported that donepezil prolongs QT
20 interval not only by I_{Kr} block but also by I_{Kr} trafficking inhibition⁴⁰. Additionally, QT prolongation
21 by dasatinib, is also partially due to its effects on intracellular PI3K signaling⁴¹. Cilostazol is a
22 phosphodiesterase 3 (PED3) inhibitor that induces intracellular cAMP elevation, Ca^{2+} dynamic
23 unbalance and early afterdepolarizations (EADs)⁴², which could favor TdP. Dronedarone is known

1 to transform into N-debutyl-dronedarone⁴³, a metabolite that retains up to one third of the parent's
2 activity. Since both show important channel blocking effects, not considering dronedarone's main
3 metabolite might be the cause of its misclassification. As for saquinavir, it could be related to
4 presence of higher levels in myocardium than in blood plasma⁴⁴, increasing the odds of producing
5 adverse effects in this tissue. Finally, other factors can be related to the misclassification of
6 ofloxacin, quetiapine, ranolazine, lamotrigine and eltrombopag. Although ofloxacin has been
7 classified as a Class 2 compound by CredibleMeds, rare cases of TdP have been reported in
8 patients receiving it^{45,46} and experimental data has showed that ofloxacin does not provoke APD
9 prolongation in rabbit Purkinje fibers⁴⁷, which are cells prone to APD prolongation. In our work
10 we performed a large number of simulations to take into account the block effect if the drugs on
11 the three main channels (I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} and I_{CaL}), but a few drugs in our dataset show blocking effects on
12 the Na^+ channels, namely, quetiapine, ranolazine and lamotrigine. Finally, it is worth noting that
13 eltrombopag showed high variability of its IC_{50} and its classification was uncertain as there is a
14 lack of strong evidence for placing it in any QT risk category³¹.

15 This study is also in line with current initiatives aiming to define a new paradigm in cardiac safety
16 like CiPA (Comprehensive In vitro Proarrhythmia Assay)²², where modeling and simulation of the
17 human cellular ventricular electrophysiology will play a relevant role in the assessment of the
18 proarrhythmic risk of drugs.

19 *4.5 Limitations of the study*

20 One of the values of this work is the use of a large training series, since we consider that this allows
21 obtaining a more realistic estimation of the prediction errors. However, the I_{Ks} and I_{CaL} IC_{50} values
22 of some compounds were not available from the literature and it was assumed that the block of

1 these channels was negligible, similarly to previous works^{12,16}. In addition, the IC₅₀ values were
2 obtained from heterogeneous sources and it can be assumed that the experimental conditions were
3 diverse. However, we avoided major sources of variability by selecting IC₅₀ values registered in
4 mammalian ventricular tissues when available and discarding those extracted from *Xenopus*
5 oocytes (as described in the Methods section). We considered that all published data represents a
6 distribution of values affected by random error, plus variability due to differences in the
7 experimental conditions. From this distribution, we picked the value at the center (the median), as
8 a pragmatic approach to summarize all these values into a single one. Median is a robust estimator
9 of the central tendency of a data sample, less sensitive to the presence of extreme values, and for
10 this reason it was preferred over the average.

11 Our method does not include drug effects on Na⁺ channels, which is related to the misclassification
12 of quetiapine, ranolazine and lamotrigine, which can significantly block Na⁺ channels at EFTPC.
13 Future work will include this channel.

14 In our model, drug-channel interactions are simulated using the simple pore block model, which
15 may be too simplistic. Consideration of the Hill coefficient of the sigmoidal curve fitted to the
16 concentration–current response curves could provide little benefit, as suggested by other
17 authors^{15,16,31}. Moreover, drug binding kinetics have not been considered in this paper, although
18 they have been related to increased susceptibility to acquired long QT syndrome in the presence
19 of hERG channel kinetic abnormalities²⁶. Also, our simulations do not consider other aspects of
20 the compounds, such as pharmacokinetics/pharmacodynamics, physiology impact, metabolites or
21 drug-drug interactions. It would have enriched the results of this study, unfortunately there is a
22 lack of experimental data for the inclusion of these phenomena for all the compounds considered
23 in this study.

1 In this work, compounds have been classified using the clinical human torsadogenic risk
2 classification from CredibleMeds, which feeds from clinical data³¹. However, some of the
3 compounds used in this study are classified differently in other sources, such as Amiodarone,
4 Clarithromycin, Clozapine, Domperidone, Donepezil, Lapatinib, Moxifloxacin or Ranolazine²¹.
5 Indeed, a large number of compounds with contradicting classification have been listed by
6 Wisniowska and Polak²¹, who raise the need of a standardized classification for drug
7 proarrhythmicity risk.

8 **5. Conclusions**

9 In this study, we introduce a new in silico tool to predict the effect of a drug on the APD and QT
10 prolongation and its proarrhythmic risk using the valuable Tx index. It takes into account both the
11 maximum EFTPC and the multichannel effect of the drugs. Although, there is no doubt about the
12 high influence of the hERG block of a drug on the QT prolongation and the likelihood of TdP, our
13 results highlight the need of considering the EFTPC and the blocking effects on the different
14 channels of a drug for improving the prediction of cardiotoxicity, factors that are integrated in the
15 Tx index. This work contributes to Comprehensive in-vitro Proarrhythmia Assay (CiPA) initiative
16 by using an in silico human model to obtain a more accurate prediction of human QT and pro-
17 arrhythmic risk of TdP. Our results show that all these four tests based on Tx provide very similar
18 predictions and that good torsadogenic risk predictions can be obtained based on the endocardial
19 APD prolongation ($Tx-APD_{Endo}$) of human isolated cells. This test could be used to predict the
20 human QT prolongation caused by a compound in the different phases of drug discovery only
21 using a test concentration and the blocking potency of the compound to I_{Kr} , I_{Ks} , and I_{CaL} , or even
22 to obtain an estimate of the maximum safe free plasma concentration that prevents excessive QT
23 and APD prolongations.

1 **Supporting Information**

2 Supporting Information available:

- 3 - Table S1: Drug dataset (Risk class, EFTPC, pIC₅₀, EFTPC calculation) with all references.
- 4 - Table S2: Simulation results (QT intervals, APD₉₀, Tx-QT and Tx-APD₉₀).
- 5 - Table S3: Tx-APD_{Endo} ROC curves at 0.5, 1 and 2 Hz pacing rates.

6 AUTHOR INFORMATION

7 **Corresponding author**

8 Javier Saiz*.

9 Centro de Investigación e Innovación en Bioingeniería (CI2B),

10 Universitat Politècnica de València,

11 Camino de Vera s/n, 46022, Valencia, SPAIN.

12 Tel: +34 96 3877000 ext. 76025.

13 Fax: +34 96 3877093.

14 e-mail: jsaiz@ci2b.upv.es

15 **Contact Information**

16 Lucia Romero[‡]: lurope@ci2b.upv.es

17 Jordi Cano[‡]: jordi.cg89@gmail.com

1 Julio Gomis-Tena: jgomiste@ci2b.upv.es

2 Beatriz Trenor: btrenor@ci2b.upv.es

3 Ferran Sanz: ferran.sanz@upf.edu

4 Manuel Pastor: manuel.pastor@upf.edu

5 Javier Saiz: jsaiz@ci2b.upv.es

6 **Author Contributions**

7 ‡ Lucia Romero and Jordi Cano contributed equally to this work.

8 **ACKNOWLEDGMENTS**

9 L.R., J.C., J.G., B.T., J.S.: This work was partially supported by the Dirección General de Política
10 Científica de la Generalitat Valenciana (PROMETEU2016/088) as well as Ministerio de Economía
11 y Competitividad and Fondo Europeo de Desarrollo Regional (FEDER) DPI2015-69125-R
12 (MINECO/FEDER, UE). F.S, M.P.: received support from the Innovative Medicines Initiative
13 (IMI) Joint Undertaking under grant agreement n° 115002 (eTOX), resources of which are
14 composed of financial contribution from the European Union's Seventh Framework Programme
15 (FP7/2007-2013) and EFPIA companies' in-kind contributions.

16 **Conflict of interest**

17 The authors declare no competing financial interest.

18 **ABBREVIATIONS**

- 1 APD_x: Action Potential Duration at X% repolarization.
- 2 CiPA: Comprehensive in vitro Proarrhythmia Assay.
- 3 D₁₀: Drug dose that produces a 10% increase in the APD₉₀ of a single cell simulation or QT interval
- 4 of the ECG.
- 5 EAD: Early After Depolarization.
- 6 ECG: Electrocardiogram.
- 7 EFTPC: Effective Free Therapeutic Plasma Concentration (peak).
- 8 hERG: Ether-à-go-go Related Gene encoding the pore-forming alpha-subunit of the rapid
- 9 component of delayed rectifier current (I_{Kr}) channels in Humans.
- 10 IC₅₀: Half Maximal Inhibitory Concentration.
- 11 I_{CaL}: Calcium type-L ion channel current.
- 12 I_{Kr}: Rapid component of the delayed rectifier potassium current.
- 13 I_{Ks}: Slow component of the delayed rectifier potassium current.
- 14 ORd: O'Hara-Rudy model of the human ventricular cell³⁰.
- 15 pIC₅₀: negative logarithm of the IC₅₀.
- 16 QT: Time interval between the start of the Q wave and the end of the T wave in an ECG.
- 17 ROC: Receiver Operating Characteristic.
- 18 TdP: Torsade-de-Pointes.
- 19 TNR: True Negative Rate.
- 20 TPR: True Positive Rate.
- 21 XO: Xenopus oocytes.

22 REFERENCES

- 23 (1) Hammond, T. G.; Carlsson, L.; Davis, A. S.; Lynch, W. G.; MacKenzie, I.; Redfern, W.
- 24 S.; Sullivan, A. T.; Camm, A. J. Methods of Collecting and Evaluating Non-Clinical
- 25 Cardiac Electrophysiology Data in the Pharmaceutical Industry: Results of an

- 1 International Survey. *Cardiovasc. Res.* **2001**, *49* (4), 741–750.
- 2 (2) Recanatini, M.; Poluzzi, E.; Masetti, M.; Cavalli, A.; De Ponti, F. QT Prolongation
3 through hERG K⁺ Channel Blockade: Current Knowledge and Strategies for the Early
4 Prediction during Drug Development. *Medicinal Research Reviews*. March 2005, pp 133–
5 166.
- 6 (3) Noble, D. Computational Models of the Heart and Their Use in Assessing the Actions of
7 Drugs. *J. Pharmacol. Sci. (Amsterdam, Netherlands)* **2008**, *107* (2), 107–117.
- 8 (4) Valentin, J.-P.; Hammond, T. Safety and Secondary Pharmacology: Successes, Threats,
9 Challenges and Opportunities. *J. Pharmacol. Toxicol. Methods* **2008**, *58* (2), 77–87.
- 10 (5) Adams, C. P.; Brantner, V. V. Estimating the Cost of New Drug Development: Is It Really
11 802 Million Dollars? *Health Aff.* **2006**, *25* (2), 420–428.
- 12 (6) ICH. Harmonised Tripartite Guideline S7B. Non-clinical Evaluation of the Potential for
13 Delayed Ventricular Repolarization (QT Interval Prolongation) by Human
14 Pharmaceuticals. Step 4 Version, May 2005.
15 [http://www.ich.org/fileadmin/Public_Web_Site/ICH_Products/Guidelines/Efficacy/E14/E](http://www.ich.org/fileadmin/Public_Web_Site/ICH_Products/Guidelines/Efficacy/E14/E14_Guideline.pdf)
16 [14_Guideline.pdf](http://www.ich.org/fileadmin/Public_Web_Site/ICH_Products/Guidelines/Efficacy/E14/E14_Guideline.pdf).
- 17 (7) ICH. Harmonised Tripartite Guideline E14. Clinical Evaluation of QT/QTc Interval
18 Prolongation and Proarrhythmic Potential for Non-antiarrhythmic Drugs. Step 4 Version,
19 May 2005
20 [https://www.fda.gov/downloads/Drugs/GuidanceComplianceRegulatoryInformation/Guid](https://www.fda.gov/downloads/Drugs/GuidanceComplianceRegulatoryInformation/Guidances/UCM073153.pdf)
21 [ances/UCM073153.pdf](https://www.fda.gov/downloads/Drugs/GuidanceComplianceRegulatoryInformation/Guidances/UCM073153.pdf).

- 1 (8) Roden, D. M. Cellular Basis of Drug-Induced Torsades de Pointes. *Br. J. Pharmacol.*
2 **2008**, *154* (7), 1502–1507.
- 3 (9) Kramer, J.; Obejero-Paz, C. A.; Myatt, G.; Kuryshev, Y. A.; Bruening-Wright, A.;
4 Verducci, J. S.; Brown, A. M. MICE Models: Superior to the HERG Model in Predicting
5 Torsade de Pointes. *Sci. Rep.* **2013**, *3* (1), 2100.
- 6 (10) Windley, M. J.; Abi-Gerges, N.; Fermini, B.; Hancox, J. C.; Vandenberg, J. I.; Hill, A. P.
7 Measuring Kinetics and Potency of hERG Block for CiPA. *J. Pharmacol. Toxicol.*
8 *Methods* **2017**.
- 9 (11) Pollard, C. E.; Abi Gerges, N.; Bridgland-Taylor, M. H.; Easter, A.; Hammond, T. G.;
10 Valentin, J.-P. An Introduction to QT Interval Prolongation and Non-Clinical Approaches
11 to Assessing and Reducing Risk. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* **2010**, *159* (1), 12–21.
- 12 (12) Mirams, G. R.; Cui, Y.; Sher, A.; Fink, M.; Cooper, J.; Heath, B. M.; McMahon, N. C.;
13 Gavaghan, D. J.; Noble, D. Simulation of Multiple Ion Channel Block Provides Improved
14 Early Prediction of Compounds' Clinical Torsadogenic Risk. *Cardiovasc. Res.* **2011**, *91*
15 (1), 53–61.
- 16 (13) Obiol-Pardo, C.; Gomis-Tena, J.; Sanz, F.; Saiz, J.; Pastor, M. A Multiscale Simulation
17 System for the Prediction of Drug-Induced Cardiotoxicity. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **2011**, *51*
18 (2), 483–492.
- 19 (14) Davies, M. R.; Mistry, H. B.; Hussein, L.; Pollard, C. E.; Valentin, J.-P.; Swinton, J.; Abi-
20 Gerges, N. An in Silico Canine Cardiac Midmyocardial Action Potential Duration Model
21 as a Tool for Early Drug Safety Assessment. *Am. J. Physiol. Heart Circ. Physiol.* **2012**,

- 1 302 (7), 1466–1480.
- 2 (15) Beattie, K. A.; Luscombe, C.; Williams, G.; Munoz-Muriedas, J.; Gavaghan, D. J.; Cui,
3 Y.; Mirams, G. R. Evaluation of an in Silico Cardiac Safety Assay: Using Ion Channel
4 Screening Data to Predict QT Interval Changes in the Rabbit Ventricular Wedge. *J.*
5 *Pharmacol. Toxicol. Methods* **2013**, *68* (1), 88–96.
- 6 (16) Mirams, G. R.; Davies, M. R.; Brough, S. J.; Bridgland-Taylor, M. H.; Cui, Y.; Gavaghan,
7 D. J.; Abi-Gerges, N. Prediction of Thorough QT Study Results Using Action Potential
8 Simulations Based on Ion Channel Screens. *J. Pharmacol. Toxicol. Methods* **2014**, *70* (3),
9 246–254.
- 10 (17) Yap, C. W.; Cai, C. Z.; Xue, Y.; Chen, Y. Z. Prediction of Torsade-Causing Potential of
11 Drugs by Support Vector Machine Approach. *Toxicol. Sci.* **2004**, *79* (1), 170–177.
- 12 (18) He, Y.; Lim, S. W. Y.; Yap, C. W. Determination of Torsade-Causing Potential of Drug
13 Candidates Using One-Class Classification and Ensemble Modelling Approaches. *Curr.*
14 *Drug Saf.* **2012**, *7* (4), 298–308.
- 15 (19) Mistry, H. B.; Davies, M. R.; Di Veroli, G. Y. A New Classifier-Based Strategy for in-
16 Silico Ion-Channel Cardiac Drug Safety Assessment. *Front. Pharmacol.* **2015**, *6* (MAR),
17 59.
- 18 (20) Lancaster, M. C.; Sobie, E. A. Improved Prediction of Drug-Induced Torsades de Pointes
19 Through Simulations of Dynamics and Machine Learning Algorithms. *Clin. Pharmacol.*
20 *Ther.* **2016**, *100* (4), 371–379.

- 1 (21) Wiśniowska, B.; Polak, S. Am I or Am I Not Proarrhythmic? Comparison of Various
2 Classifications of Drug TdP Propensity. *Drug Discov. Today* **2017**, *22* (1), 10–16.
- 3 (22) Sager, P. T.; Gintant, G.; Turner, J. R.; Pettit, S.; Stockbridge, N. Rechanneling the
4 Cardiac Proarrhythmia Safety Paradigm: A Meeting Report from the Cardiac Safety
5 Research Consortium. *Am. Heart J.* **2014**, *167* (3), 292–300.
- 6 (23) Redfern, W. S.; Carlsson, L.; Davis, A. S.; Lynch, W. G.; MacKenzie, I.; Palethorpe, S.;
7 Siegl, P. K. S.; Strang, I.; Sullivan, A. T.; Wallis, R.; Camm, A. J.; Hammond, T. G.
8 Relationships between Preclinical Cardiac Electrophysiology, Clinical QT Interval
9 Prolongation and Torsade de Pointes for a Broad Range of Drugs: Evidence for a
10 Provisional Safety Margin in Drug Development. *Cardiovasc. Res.* **2003**, *58* (1), 32–45.
- 11 (24) Gintant, G. An Evaluation of hERG Current Assay Performance: Translating Preclinical
12 Safety Studies to Clinical QT Prolongation. *Pharmacol. Ther.* **2011**, *129* (2), 109–119.
- 13 (25) Rodriguez, B.; Burrage, K.; Gavaghan, D.; Grau, V.; Kohl, P.; Noble, D. The Systems
14 Biology Approach to Drug Development: Application to Toxicity Assessment of Cardiac
15 Drugs. *Clin. Pharmacol. Ther.* **2010**, *88* (1), 130–134.
- 16 (26) Romero, L.; Trenor, B.; Yang, P.-C.; Saiz, J.; Clancy, C. E. In Silico Screening of the
17 Impact of hERG Channel Kinetic Abnormalities on Channel Block and Susceptibility to
18 Acquired Long QT Syndrome. *J. Mol. Cell. Cardiol.* **2015**, *87*, 271–282
- 19 (27) Trenor, B.; Gomis-Tena, J.; Cardona, K.; Romero, L.; Rajamani, S.; Belardinelli, L.;
20 Giles, W. R.; Saiz, J. In Silico Assessment of Drug Safety in Human Heart Applied to
21 Late Sodium Current Blockers. *Channels* **2013**, *7* (4), 249–262.

- 1 (28) Okada, J. -i.; Yoshinaga, T.; Kurokawa, J.; Washio, T.; Furukawa, T.; Sawada, K.;
2 Sugiura, S.; Hisada, T. Screening System for Drug-Induced Arrhythmogenic Risk
3 Combining a Patch Clamp and Heart Simulator. *Sci. Adv.* **2015**, *1* (4), 142.
- 4 (29) Mirams, G. R.; Davies, M. R.; Cui, Y.; Kohl, P.; Noble, D. Application of Cardiac
5 Electrophysiology Simulations to pro-Arrhythmic Safety Testing. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* **2012**,
6 *167* (5), 932–945.
- 7 (30) O’Hara, T.; Virág, L.; Varró, A.; Rudy, Y. Simulation of the Undiseased Human Cardiac
8 Ventricular Action Potential: Model Formulation and Experimental Validation. *PLoS*
9 *Comput. Biol.* **2011**, *7* (5), e1002061.
- 10 (31) Woosley, R.; Romero, K. www.Crediblemeds.org, QTdrugs List, AZCERT, Inc. 1822
11 Innovation Park Dr., Oro Valley, AZ 85755.
- 12 (32) Bottino, D.; Penland, R. C.; Stamps, A.; Traebert, M.; Dumotier, B.; Georgiva, A.;
13 Helmlinger, G.; Lett, G. S. Preclinical Cardiac Safety Assessment of Pharmaceutical
14 Compounds Using an Integrated Systems-Based Computer Model of the Heart. *Prog.*
15 *Biophys. Mol. Biol.* **2006**, *90* (1–3), 414–443.
- 16 (33) Brennan, T.; Fink, M.; Rodriguez, B. Multiscale Modelling of Drug-Induced Effects on
17 Cardiac Electrophysiological Activity. *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.* **2009**, *36* (1), 62–77.
- 18 (34) Elkins, R. C.; Davies, M. R.; Brough, S. J.; Gavaghan, D. J.; Cui, Y.; Abi-Gerges, N.;
19 Mirams, G. R. Variability in High-Throughput Ion-Channel Screening Data and
20 Consequences for Cardiac Safety Assessment. *J. Pharmacol. Toxicol. Methods* **2013**, *68*
21 (1), 112–122.

- 1 (35) Hoffmann, P.; Warner, B. Are hERG Channel Inhibition and QT Interval Prolongation All
2 There Is in Drug-Induced Torsadogenesis? A Review of Emerging Trends. *J. Pharmacol.*
3 *Toxicol. Methods* **2006**, *53* (2), 87–105.
- 4 (36) Cantilena, L.; Koerner, J.; Temple, R.; Throckmorton, D. FDA Evaluation of Cardiac
5 Repolarization Data for 19 Drugs and Drug Candidates. *Clin. Pharmacol. Ther.* **2006**, *79*
6 (2), 29.
- 7 (37) Virág, L.; Iost, N.; Opincariu, M.; Szolnoky, J.; Szécsi, J.; Bogáts, G.; Szenohradszky, P.;
8 Varró, A.; Papp, J. G. The Slow Component of the Delayed Rectifier Potassium Current in
9 Undiseased Human Ventricular Myocytes. *Cardiovasc. Res.* **2001**, *49* (4), 790–797.
- 10 (38) Romero, L.; Carbonell, B.; Trenor, B.; Rodríguez, B.; Saiz, J.; Ferrero, J. M. Systematic
11 Characterization of the Ionic Basis of Rabbit Cellular Electrophysiology Using Two
12 Ventricular Models. *Prog. Biophys. Mol. Biol.* **2011**, *107* (1), 60–73.
- 13 (39) Zicha, S.; Moss, I.; Allen, B.; Varro, A.; Papp, J.; Dumaine, R.; Antzelevich, C.; Nattel, S.
14 Molecular Basis of Species-Specific Expression of Repolarizing K⁺ Currents in the Heart.
15 *Am. J. Physiol. Heart Circ. Physiol.* **2003**, *285* (4), 1641–1649.
- 16 (40) Cubeddu, L. X. Drug-Induced Inhibition and Trafficking Disruption of Ion Channels:
17 Pathogenesis of QT Abnormalities and Drug-Induced Fatal Arrhythmias. *Curr. Cardiol.*
18 *Rev.* **2016**, *12* (2), 141–154.
- 19 (41) Damrongwatanasuk, R.; Fradley, M. G. Cardiovascular Complications of Targeted
20 Therapies for Chronic Myeloid Leukemia. *Curr. Treat. Options Cardiovasc. Med.* **2017**,
21 *19* (4), 24.

- 1 (42) Kanlop, N.; Chattipakorn, S.; Chattipakorn, N. Effects of Cilostazol in the Heart. *J.*
2 *Cardiovasc. Med.* **2011**, *12* (2), 88–95.
- 3 (43) Iram, F.; Ali, S.; Ahmad, A.; Khan, S. A.; Husain, A. A Review on Dronedarone:
4 Pharmacological, Pharmacodynamic and Pharmacokinetic Profile. *J. Acute Dis.* **2016**, *5*
5 (2), 102–108.
- 6 (44) Zhang, X.; Jordan, P.; Cristea, L.; Salgo, M.; Farha, R.; Kolis, S.; Lee, L. S. Thorough
7 QT/QTc Study of Ritonavir-Boosted Saquinavir Following Multiple-Dose Administration
8 of Therapeutic and Supratherapeutic Doses in Healthy Participants. *J. Clin. Pharmacol.*
9 **2012**, *52* (4), 520–529.
- 10 (45) Poluzzi, E.; Raschi, E.; Motola, D.; Moretti, U.; De Ponti, F. Antimicrobials and the Risk
11 of Torsades de Pointes: The Contribution from Data Mining of the US FDA Adverse
12 Event Reporting System. *Drug Saf.* **2010**, *33* (4), 303–314.
- 13 (46) Briasoulis, A.; Agarwal, V.; Pierce, W. J. QT Prolongation and Torsade de Pointes
14 Induced by Fluoroquinolones: Infrequent Side Effects from Commonly Used Medications.
15 *Cardiology* **2011**, *120* (2), 103–110.
- 16 (47) Adamantidis, M. M.; Dumotier, B. M.; Caron, J. F.; Bordet, R. Sparfloxacin but Not
17 Levofloxacin or Ofloxacin Prolongs Cardiac Repolarization in Rabbit Purkinje Fibers.
18 *Fundam. Clin. Pharmacol.* **1998**, *12* (1), 70–76.

19

20

1

Supporting Information

In silico QT and APD Prolongation Assay for Early Screening of Drug-induced Proarrhythmic Risk

Lucia Romero^{a‡}, Jordi Cano^{a‡}, Julio Gomis-Tena^a, Beatriz Trenor^a, Ferran Sanz^b, Manuel Pastor^b, Javier Saiz^{a}*

^a Centro de Investigación e Innovación en Bioingeniería (CI²B), Universitat Politècnica de València, camino de Vera, s/n, 46022 Valencia, Spain.

^b Research Programme on Biomedical Informatics (GRIB), Institut Hospital del Mar d'Investigacions Mèdiques (IMIM), Department. of Experimental and Health Sciences, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, carrer del Dr. Aiguader, 88, 08002 Barcelona, Spain.

**Corresponding Author e-mail: jsaiz@ci2b.upv.es*

Table S1. Drug parameters and references.

Name (1st column), torsadogenic risk (2nd column and color-coded background of first column: red (Class 1), orange (Class 2), bright green (Class 3) and dark green (Class 4)), pIC₅₀ values for hERG, I_{Ks} and I_{CaL} (3rd to 5th column), the EFTPC (6th column) and references for the pIC₅₀ values for hERG, I_{Ks} and I_{CaL} (7th to 9th column), the EFTPC (10th column). A dash in the IC₅₀ boxes means that no value was found in public databases neither in the scientific literature. 10th to 14th correspond to parameters found in given sources (see table header) and used to calculate EFTPC values.

EFTPC values (in nM) calculated as follows: $EFTPC = 10^9 \cdot (1 - f_b) \cdot \frac{MC}{MW}$ where MC is the concentration of the drug in g.L⁻¹ and MW is the molecular weight of the compound in g.mol⁻¹.

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- EFTPC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug		pIC50								Protein Bound Fraction (<i>f_b</i>)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit
Name	Class	hERG	I _{Ks}	I _{CaL}	EFTPC (nM)	Ref. I _{Kr}	Ref. I _{Ks}	Ref. I _{CaL}	Ref. EFTPC					
Ajmaline	1	5.98	-	-	1500	[15]	-	-	[15]					
Amiodarone	1	6.38	5.59	6.57	63.5	25127758, 15272206, 21489024, 15936217, 21158687, 11238279, [12], 19673885, 15817093, [11], Okada 2015, 22303293, 15541373, 15950494, 18006430, 18587422, 20493497	11238279, 15817093, 15817093, 15817093	[15]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=b0eb6c22-7553-4e3f-a06d-20a186ced99a	0.999	63535.20	645.3116	41	µg/mL
Astemizole	1	8.22	-	5.98	0.3	25127758, 15272206, 15936217, 15172012, 21158687, [12], 19673885, Okada 2015, 23137660, 18701618, 22303293, 8001268, 21675869, 15740727, 12388285, 15950494, 10376921	-	[12], 26601174	[12]					

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- ETFPC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug		pIC50								Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit	
Name	Class	hERG	I _{ks}	ICaL	ETFPC (nM)	Ref. I _{kr}	Ref. I _{ks}	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFPC						
Bepridil	1	7.16	5.10	6.08	33	9765513, 14975710, 15936217, 19616638, 15172012, 21158687, 15385083, [12], 19673885, Okada 2015, 22303293, 15950494, 16843688, 26616666.	9765513, 10588929	14975710, 2420970, [15], 19367686	[15]						
Chlorpromazine	1	5.81	3.00	4.15	66.4	21158687, 16051556, [12], 23137660, Tie 2000/Tie 2002	[14]	[12]	[15]						
Cilostazol	1	4.86	-	4.04	162.4	[12]	[12]	[12]	http://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2015/020863s0231bl.pdf	0.95	3247.98	369.46068	1200	ng/mL	
Cisapride	1	7.68	5.47	4.56	4.9	14975928, 25127758, 23201772, 9223557, 15272206, 10407390, 15574182, 23103500, 9445174, 11961040, 23651875, 23934164, 14975710, 15306208, 15936217, 19616638, 15172012, 21158687, 15385083, [12], Lacerda 2001, 15967876, 15076220, 18034998, 20172036, 9374794, Okada 2015, 12729675, 18701618,	[13]	15067213, 14975710	[15]						

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- ETFPC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug		pIC50								Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit	
Name	Class	hERG	Iks	ICaL	ETFPC (nM)	Ref. Ikr	Ref. Iks	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFPC						
						22303293, 11714889, 9395068, 17531263, 21675869, 15740727, 17928736, 10510456, 12388285, 15950494, 18587422, 16843688, Yamazaki 2014									
Clarithromycin	1	4.06	-	-	4011	12065733, 10219239, 17531263, 14674677	-	-	https://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=8a56f36f-4e45-43f6-842b-5c2d319aaec	0.7	13369.82	747.95336	10	µg/mL	
Disopyramide	1	5.00	4.09	4.96	4713	[19], 21989164, 23137660, 16842817, 15272206, 11162661, 15950494	[19]	[19]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=11a68e26-d2e4-48f6-ba0f-9bdd5778f25a	0.6	11782.92	339.47446	4	µg/mL	
Dofetilide	1	7.75	-	-	2	22391528, 1501123, 21224008, 9501201, 15574182, 23103500, 21489024, Frederiksen 2001, 20071423, 15936217, 15172012, 22074238, 21158687, 8417848, 14711935, [12], 14525949, Lacerda 2001, 22609836, 17042915, 18493243, 19673885, 20172036, [16], Okada 2015, 12729675, 18701618, 22303293, 9395068,	21224008	21224008	[15]						

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- ETFPC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug		pIC50								Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit	
Name	Class	hERG	I _{ks}	ICaL	ETFPC (nM)	Ref. I _{kr}	Ref. I _{ks}	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFPC						
						9694935, 21675869, 8649354, 11927665, 7882490, 26616666, 4722980									
Domperidone	1	6.88	-	-	5.79	15640612, 11034933, 19673885, 15950494	-	-	[2]		0.92	72.39	425.911	30.83	ng/mL
Donepezil	1	6.16	-	4.47	6.56	[12]	-	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=11ac01f4-d26e-47b2-9660-d514ab097fdb	0.96	164.00				
Dronedarone	1	7.29	5.00	6.75	0.79	15541373, 21777565	[7]	[7]	https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/208898#section=Absorption-Distribution-and-Excretion	0.997	264.03	556.75646	147	ng/mL	
Droperidol	1	7.22	-	5.12	16	[12]	-	[12]	[12]						
Flecainide	1	5.82	-	4.57	1448	[12]	-	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=72595783-e6a0-6b7a-f428-9ca03d707794	0.4	2413.46	414.342719	1	µg/mL	
Halofantrine	1	6.42	-	5.72	172	[12]	-	[12]	[12]						
Haloperidol	1	7.44	-	5.77	3.6	19673885, 15076220, 23137660, 12729675, 22303293, 18587422, 16843688, 25127758, 10407390, 11961040, 23651875, 20862641, Frederiksen 2001, 15936217, 19616638, 21158687, 16278312, 15385083, [12]	-	[15]	[15]						
Ibutilide	1	7.75	-	4.20	22	[12]	-	[12]	https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/60753#section=Absorption-Distribution-and-Excretion	0.4	15.08	384.57644	14.4	ng/mL	

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- ETFFPC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug		pIC50								Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit
Name	Class	hERG	Iks	ICaL	ETFFPC (nM)	Ref. Ikr	Ref. Iks	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFFPC					
Levofloxacin	1	3.37	-	-	30932	16474415, 20662825, 11125032	-	-	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=8962eb50-3366-1eec-44f9-170e686d2d66	0.31	33483.92	361.367503	16.2	µg/mL
Methadone	1	5.46	-	4.43	507	[12]	-	[12]	[12]					
Moxifloxacin	1	4.11	3.80	3.40	6228	16474415, 16158069, Thomsen 2006, 19673885, 22289150, 17054943, 16474415, 11040340, 21224008, 11125032, 14512100, 15076220, 18587422.	[16]	[12], [16], Okada 2015	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=71b02da1-3175-1db8-192a-c0a8a6cd98a5	0.5	11209.89	401.431363	5	mg/L
Ondansetron	1	6.09	3.00	-	178.6	11046096	11046096	-	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=2edc0788-dc38-4d21-ba8e-71f159e2d3b1	0.73	662.66	293.36296	194.4	ng/mL
Procainamide	1	3.57	-	3.41	35058	[12]	-	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=17e47845-daad-434c-a784-6d3875b0d704	0.175	42494.36	235.32534	10	µg/mL
Quinidine	1	5.90	4.36	4.81	2960	15936217, 21362439, 16842817, 11561091, 18701618, 18587422, 15385083, 21996251, 17042915, 17042915, 17042915, 17042915, Wang, 21224008, 21996251, 17604185, 15172012, 21158687, 15385083, 15385083, 15385083, 12086981, 15950494, 11927665, 19617705,	11561091	[15], 21224008, 12180412	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=11d14362-8f69-4c30-b487-5d05f6462bd7	0.84	18500			

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- ETFPC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug		pIC50								Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit	
Name	Class	hERG	Iks	ICaL	ETFPC (nM)	Ref. Ikr	Ref. Iks	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFPC						
						19617705, 10648647, 15821840, 15821840, 15821840, 12695533, 12695533, 15189761, 10028924									
Sotalol	1	3.29	-	-	18358	19673885, 18701618, 18587422, 15385083, 22074238, 23137660, Wang, 21224008, 17604185, 15172012, 15385083, 15385083, 15385083, 16757186, 15821840, 15821840	21224008	21224008	Danda Hilal-Dandan, Laurence L. Brunton, Goodman & Gilman's Manual of Pharmacology and Therapeutics 2nd Edition, McGrawHill. P. 513.						
Sparfloxacin	1	4.66	-	4.05	1766	[12]	-	[12]	[12]						
Tedisamil	1	6.66	5.19	-	85	[15]	15579009	-	[15]						
Terfenadine	1	7.30	5.36	6.51	9	25127758, 9690857, 21224008, 10407390, 10604956, 15574182, 16782359, 11961040, 14975710, 20071423, 15936217, 15172012, Helson 2012, 21158687, 16278312, 15385083, [12], Lacerda 2001, 17042915, 22300168, 19673885, 15076220, Okada 2015, 23137660,	[13]	14975710, [15], 21224008, 9242181	[12]						

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- ETFPC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug	pIC50					ETFPC	Ref. Ikr	Ref. Iks	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFPC	Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit
						12729675, 18701618, 22303293, 9395068, 8001268, 21675869, 15740727, 12388285, 15950494, 18587422, 16843688									
Terodiline	1	6.71	4.56	4.87	11.23	19673885, 21158687, 17110801	[6]	[6]	[10]						
Thioridazine	1	6.70	4.99	5.88	979	15936217, 19673885, Tie 2000/Tie 2002, 16051556, 12176106, 15385083, 23137660, 17056009, 16278312, 21224008, 11961040, 21158687, 15950494	10027867, 21224008	[15], 21224008	[15]						
Clozapine	2	5.64	-	5.44	70.8	11961040, Frederiksen 2001, 19616638, 21158687, [12], Tie 2002	-	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=d5c8a456-6f3c-4963-b321-4ed746f690e4	0.97	2359.07	326.82326	771	ng/mL	
Dasatinib	2	4.80	3.60	3.40	20.4	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]						
Lapatinib	2	6.00	3.60	2.70	41.8	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=63319b01-cad6-4d0a-c39b-938fa951a808	0.99	4182.03	581.057543	2.43	µg/mL	
Nilotinib	2	6.90	3.40	3.70	60	[16]	[16]	[16]	[8]						
Ofloxacin	2	2.85	-	-	8656	11125032	-	-	https://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=1d19a6db-6da5-e7de-f929-2d18bdfa2cf5	0.32	12729.42	361.3675	4.6	µg/mL	
Paliperidone	2	5.90	3.60	3.40	68.9	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=9089db76-aa50-417d-bf62-3674df161e9a	0.74	264.96	426.483883	113	ng/mL	
Risperidone	2	6.63	5.01	4.14	6.96	19673885, 12775973,	[13]	14975710, [12], [15]	[18]						

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- ETFPC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug	pIC50					ETFPC (nM)	Ref. Ikr	Ref. Iks	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFPC	Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit
Name	Class	hERG	Iks	ICaL	ETFPC (nM)	Ref. Ikr	Ref. Iks	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFPC	Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit	
						12176106, 14975710, 21224008, 11961040, 21158687, 15950494.									
Saquinavir	2	4.77	-	5.72	334	[12]	-	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=c00d1607-ac36-457b-a34b-75ad74f9cf0a	0.98	16695.47	670.8408	11.2	µg/mL	
Sunitinib	2	6.60	4.20	4.10	19	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=43a4d7f8-48ae-4a63-9108-2fa8e3ea9d9c	0.925	253.47	398.473783	101	ng/mL	
Tolterodine	2	7.90	4.10	-	0.39	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=2cad3579-d197-4019-ac94-460525b6a8d9	0.963	10.45	325.48764	3.4	ng/mL	
Metronidazole	3	2.87	-	3.75	210336	[12]	-	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=a9987047-9c99-45a5-829b-ae8b189cbfd4						
Nelfinavir	3	4.90	4.10	-	60.25	[16]	[16]	[16]	https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/64142#section=Pharmacology-and-Biochemistry	0.99	6025.11	663.88806	4	µg/mL	
Paroxetine	3	5.72	-	5.41	12.7	[12]	-	[12]	http://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2014/020031s071,020710s0351bl.pdf	0.94	211.62	329.365403	69.7	ng/mL	
Quetiapine	3	5.42	-	4.98	461.9	12176106, 21158687	-	[15]	[9]	0.83	2717.03	383.507	1042	ng/mL	
Ranolazine	3	4.90	2.72	3.51	2311	15302796, 23010360, Okada 2015, 18520952, 15950494, 19592609	15277312	15277312	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=8d442b8c-97a8-40a9-8603-f9cd0542cedc	0.62	6081.35	427.53652	2600	ng/mL	
Solifenacin	3	6.60	4.50	5.20	3.47	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2013/021518s0161bl.pdf	0.98	173.53	362.46474	62.9	ng/mL	
Voriconazole	3	3.31	-	3.38	5699	[12]	-	[12]	http://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2015/021266s038,021267s047,021630s0281bl.pdf	0.58	13569.59	349.31047	4.74	µg/mL	
Alvimopan	4	3.10	4.30	5.30	5.17	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=77a67dc6-35d3-48ff-9d18-292d4d442f70	0.8	25.86	424.53258	10.98	ng/mL	

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- ETFPFC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug	pIC50									Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit	
Name	Class	hERG	Iks	ICaL	ETFPFC (nM)	Ref. Ikr	Ref. Iks	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFPFC						
Ambrisentan	4	3.30	3.30	2.60	75.3	[16]	[16]	[16]	[8]						
Ceftriaxone	4	3.35	-	3.81	13704	[12]	-	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=2dd1be9e-74cc-48e8-bf02-f34a78d80fda	0.9	137040.66	554.57992	76	µg/mL	
Darifenacin	4	7.10	4.70	2.80	0.27	[16]	[16]	[16]	[8]						
Darunavir	4	3.80	3.50	-	862.5	[16]	[16]	[16]	[8]						
Deferasirox	4	2.40	-	3.00	1403	[16]	[16]	[16]	[8]						
Desvenlafaxine	4	3.60	-	-	3901	[16]	[16]	[16]	[16]						
Diazepam	4	4.27	-	4.52	29	[12]	-	[12]	[12]						
Diltiazem	4	4.88	-	6.12	120.6	[12]	-	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=d6a81f9f-3a51-4e86-aeb3-8352186b3528	0.75	482.49	414.51784	200	ng/mL	
Doxorubicin	4	3.00	5.32	-	4646	19703166	19703166	-	https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/31703#section=Absorption-Distribution-and-Excretion	0.75	18582.60	543.51926	10.1	µg/mL	
Duloxetine	4	5.42	5.00	5.55	9.22	[12]	[16]	[12]	[4]		0.95	184.32	297.415	54.82	ng/mL
Ebastine	4	6.14	6.10	-	0.14	9103502, 19673885	9103502	-	[3]		0.99	13.83	469.6576	6.495	ng/mL
Eltrombopag	4	6.20	-	-	158.9	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=616224ff-a925-4b38-9ca2-00fbf669380f	0.99	15888.21	442.46658	7.03	µg/mL	
Etravirine	4	3.80	2.90	-	3.38	[16]	[16]	[16]	[8]						
Everolimus	4	3.30	4.00	-	8.03	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=e082a024-7850-400b-a5c2-2a140612562a	0.74	30.89	958.22442	29.6	ng/mL	
Lamivudine	4	2.69	-	4.27	1446	[12]	-	[12]	https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/60825#section=Absorption-Distribution-and-Excretion	0.36	2259.42	663.88806	1.5	µg/mL	
Lamotrigine	4	3.60	3.80	2.80	19083	[16]	[16]	[16]	[8]						
Linezolid	4	2.94	-	3.98	24856	[12]	-	[12]	http://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2015/021130s030,021131s029,021132s034lbl.pdf	0.35	39721.82	337.346103	13.4	mg/L	
Loratadine	4	5.22	-	4.94	0.4	[12]	-	[12]	[12]						
Maraviroc	4	4.40	4.20	-	415	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=a94a9a2b-337b-4c13-8622-fc392194dc21	0.76	1728.75	513.665546	888	ng/mL	
Mibefradil	4	5.77	4.93	6.29	12	[12]	9765513	[12]	[12]						

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- ETFFPC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug		pIC50								Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit
Name	Class	hERG	Iks	ICaL	ETFFPC (nM)	Ref. Ikr	Ref. Iks	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFFPC					
Mitoxantrone	4	3.27	-	4.65	225	[12]	-	[12]	[12]					
Nebivolol	4	6.50	4.80	-	1	[16]	[16]	[16]	[8]					
Nifedipine	4	3.87	3.44	7.28	32.3	22074238, [12], 19673885, 19673885, 10924918	10924918	10900233, 10900233, 9098694, 17173968, 9846638, 19367686	[5]	0.95	646.20	346.3346	223.8	ng/mL
Nisoldipine	4	4.64	4.40	7.10	0.10	[17]	[17]	[17], 9846638	[1]	0.99	10.30	388.4144	4	ng/mL
Palonosetron	4	5.70	4.30	3.40	1.04	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=bd06f321-bb42-4748-92f3-d59626b540e0	0.62	2.73	296.40666	0.81	ng/mL
Pentobarbital	4	2.84	3.72	3.52	5171	[12]	11862331	[12]	[12]					
Phenytoin	4	3.83	3.00	4.66	3964	[12]	21224008	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=78b38e7b-1460-4adc-b738-320ffa6259c2	0.95	79280.77	252.26798	20	µg/mL
Propranolol	4	5.09	3.00	4.71	10.1	21224008, 19616638, 16314852, 23137660, 16150441, 16843688	21224008	21224008, [15]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=2d9d9660-ef3a-4abf-c291-d88d844ff658	0.9	100.64	259.34344	26.1	ng/mL
Raltegravir	4	3.11	4.60	3.61	7000	[12]	[16]	[12]	[12]					
Ribavirin	4	3.02	-	3.21	15069	[12]	-	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=35f99f76-f2ef-4a81-91ff-285419664be3	0	15069.33	244.20468	3680	ng/mL
Sildenafil	4	4.50	3.40	4.00	100	[16]	[16]	[16]	[8]					
Sildenafil	4	5.10	3.60	3.10	11.2	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=a21163d6-e1b9-4490-bcc3-751e0823797c	0.97	372.93	495.53449	184.8	ng/mL
Sitagliptin	4	3.83	3.10	3.83	589	[12]	[16]	[12]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=f85a48d0-0407-4c50-b0fa-7673a160bf01	0.38	950			
S-oxybutynin	4	4.92	4.54	4.79	0.05	[11]	10672870	10672870	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=c5950dba-d92b-46a0-993f-a9f9ddb52bf	0.99	5.04	357.48644	1.8	ng/mL
Tadalafil	4	4.00	3.80	-	50.1	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=ebddb745-81f9-4b25-8739-b2886032ed26	0.94	834.61	389.40396	325	ng/mL

- References (PMIDs and names belong to www.tox-portal.net compound database, indices between brackets link to their references at the end of this document).
- Class belongs mainly to Crediblemeds.org. All compounds that were not listed in this website were included in group 4 except for Ajmaline.
- ETFPFC values and Mass Concentrations used as the highest value of available ranges, mean + SD or directly from the highest dosage regimen.
- Protein Bound Fraction and Molecular Weight of the drugs belong to Drugbank.ca.
- Mirams et al. 2014¹⁶: We only considered "M&Q" dataset.

Drug		pIC50				ETFPFC				Protein Bound Fraction (f_b)	Molar Concentration (nM)	Molecular Weight (g/mol)	Mass Concentration	Unit
Name	Class	hERG	Iks	ICaL	ETFPFC (nM)	Ref. Ikr	Ref. Iks	Ref. ICaL	Ref. ETFPFC					
Telbivudine	4	0.80	3.60	-	14731	[16]	[16]	[16]	http://dailymed.nlm.nih.gov/dailymed/drugInfo.cfm?setid=0664309d-1342-4a63-ba5f-4b899cdf3bec	0.033	15233.55	242.22856	3.69	µg/mL

References.

1. Baksi, A. K.; Edwards, J. S.; Ahr, G. A Comparison of the Pharmacokinetics of Nisoldipine in Elderly and Young Subjects. *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* **1991**, *31* (3), 367–370.
2. Boyce, M. J.; Baisley, K. J.; Warrington, S. J. Pharmacokinetic Interaction between Domperidone and Ketoconazole Leads to QT Prolongation in Healthy Volunteers: A Randomized, Placebo-Controlled, Double-Blind, Crossover Study. *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* **2012**, *73* (3), 411–421.
3. Chaikin, P.; Gillen, M. S.; Malik, M.; Pentikis, H.; Rhodes, G. R.; Roberts, D. J. Co-Administration of Ketoconazole with H1-Antagonists Ebastine and Loratadine in Healthy Subjects: Pharmacokinetic and Pharmacodynamic Effects. *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* **2005**, *59* (3), 346–354.
4. Chan, C.; Yeo, K. P.; Pan, A. X.; Lim, M.; Knadler, M. P.; Small, D. S. Duloxetine Pharmacokinetics Are Similar in Japanese and Caucasian Subjects. *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* **2007**, *63* (3), 310–314.
5. Edwards, C.; Monkman, S.; Cholerton, S.; Rawlins, M. D.; Idle, J. R.; Ferner, R. E. Lack of Effect of Co-Trimoxazole on the Pharmacokinetics and Pharmacodynamics of Nifedipine. *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* **1990**, *30* (6), 889–891.
6. Shuba, L. M.; Kasamaki, Y.; Jones, S. E.; Ogura, T.; McCullough, J. R.; McDonald, T. F. Action Potentials, Contraction, and Membrane Currents in Guinea Pig Ventricular Preparations Treated with the Antispasmodic Agent Terodiline. *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.* **1999**, *290* (3), 1417–1426.
7. Gautier, P.; Guillemare, E.; Marion, A.; Bertrand, J.-P.; Tourneur, Y.; Nisato, D. Electrophysiologic Characterization of Dronedarone in Guinea Pig Ventricular Cells. *J. Cardiovasc. Pharmacol.* **2003**, *41* (2), 191–202.
8. Gintant, G. An Evaluation of hERG Current Assay Performance: Translating Preclinical Safety Studies to Clinical QT Prolongation. *Pharmacol. Ther.* **2011**, *129* (2), 109–119.
9. Grimm, S. W.; Richtand, N. M.; Winter, H. R.; Stams, K. R.; Reece, S. B. Effects of Cytochrome P450 3A Modulators Ketoconazole and Carbamazepine on Quetiapine Pharmacokinetics. *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* **2006**, *61* (1), 58–69.
10. Hallén, B.; Karlsson, M. O.; Stromberg, S.; Norén, B. Bioavailability and Disposition of Terodiline in Man. *J. Pharm. Sci.* **1994**, *83* (9), 1241–1246.
11. Jones, S. E.; Shuba, L. M.; Zhabyeyev, P.; McCullough, J. R.; McDonald, T. F. Differences in the Effects of Urinary Incontinence Agents S-Oxybutynin and Terodiline on Cardiac K(+) Currents and Action Potentials. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* **2000**, *131* (2), 245–254.
12. Kramer, J.; Obejero-Paz, C. A.; Myatt, G.; Kuryshev, Y. A.; Bruening-Wright, A.; Verducci, J. S.; Brown, A. M. MICE Models: Superior to the HERG Model in Predicting Torsade de Pointes. *Sci. Rep.* **2013**, *3* (1), 2100.
13. Lacerda, A. E.; Kramer, J.; Shen, K. Z.; Thomas, D.; Brown, a. M. Comparison of Block among Cloned Cardiac Potassium Channels by Non-Antiarrhythmic Drugs. *Eur. Hear. J. Suppl.* **2001**, *3* (Supplement K), 23–30.

14. Lee, S.-Y.; Choi, S.-Y.; Youm, J. B.; Ho, W.-K.; Earm, Y. E.; Lee, C. O.; Jo, S.-H. Block of HERG Human K(+) Channel and IKr of Guinea Pig Cardiomyocytes by Chlorpromazine. *J. Cardiovasc. Pharmacol.* **2004**, *43* (5), 706–714.
15. Mirams, G. R.; Cui, Y.; Sher, A.; Fink, M.; Cooper, J.; Heath, B. M.; McMahon, N. C.; Gavaghan, D. J.; Noble, D. Simulation of Multiple Ion Channel Block Provides Improved Early Prediction of Compounds' Clinical Torsadogenic Risk. *Cardiovasc. Res.* **2011**, *91* (1), 53–61.
16. Mirams, G. R.; Davies, M. R.; Brough, S. J.; Bridgland-Taylor, M. H.; Cui, Y.; Gavaghan, D. J.; Abi-Gerges, N. Prediction of Thorough QT Study Results Using Action Potential Simulations Based on Ion Channel Screens. *J. Pharmacol. Toxicol. Methods* **2014**, *70* (3), 246–254.
17. Missan, S.; Zhabyeyev, P.; Dyachok, O.; Jones, S. E.; McDonald, T. F. Block of Cardiac Delayed-Rectifier and Inward-Rectifier K⁺ Currents by Nisoldipine. *Br. J. Pharmacol.* **2003**, *140* (5), 863–870.
18. Okereke, C. S.; Kirby, L.; Kumar, D.; Cullen, E. I.; Pratt, R. D.; Hahne, W. A. Concurrent Administration of Donepezil HCl and Levodopa/carbidopa in Patients with Parkinson's Disease: Assessment of Pharmacokinetic Changes and Safety Following Multiple Oral Doses. *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* **2004**, *58 Suppl 1*, 41–49.
19. Satoh, H. Comparative Actions of Cibenzoline and Disopyramide on I(Kr) and I(Ks) Currents in Rat Sino-Atrial Nodal Cells. *Eur. J. Pharmacol.* **2000**, *407* (1–2), 123–129.

Table S2. Simulated QT interval and endocardial, midmyocardial and epicardial APD₉₀ values at the EFTPC at therapeutic doses of the drugs and Tx indices.

Name (1st column), QT interval (2nd column), endocardial, midmyocardial and epicardial APD₉₀ (3rd to 5th columns) at the EFTPC at therapeutic doses for each compound and Tx-QT (6th column), Tx-APD_{Endo}, Tx-APD_{Mid} and Tx-APD_{Epi} (7th to 9th columns).

Compound	QT _{int} (ms)	APD ₉₀ (ms)			Tx QT	Tx APD			EFTPC (nM)
		ENDO	M	EPI		ENDO	M	EPI	
Ajmaline	468	424.6	516.0	356.9	0.16	0.10	0.13	0.13	1500
Amiodarone	330	276.1	347.3	238.7	1.82	2.51	2.00	1.58	63.5
Astemizole	319	274.4	338.2	230.1	4.47	3.16	3.98	3.98	0.3
Bepriidil	376	331.1	398.0	278.0	0.48	0.40	0.50	0.40	33
Chlorpromazine	319	272.7	336.6	228.9	5.13	3.98	5.01	5.01	66.4
Cilostazol	315	268.3	332.3	225.4	18.62	15.85	19.95	15.85	162.4
Cisapride	348	303.3	367.4	253.5	0.95	0.63	0.79	0.79	4.9
Clarithromycin	319	274.4	338.2	230.1	4.79	3.16	3.98	3.98	4011
Disopyramide	369	313.6	389.5	273.5	0.60	0.50	0.50	0.40	4713
Dofetilide	331	285.8	349.7	239.3	1.95	1.26	1.58	1.58	2
Domperidone	319	272.7	336.6	228.9	5.01	3.98	5.01	5.01	5.79
Donepezil	315	268.0	331.9	225.1	23.44	15.85	19.95	19.95	6.56
Dronedarone	315	268.7	332.8	225.8	14.45	12.59	15.85	12.59	0.79
Droperidol	348	303.2	367.3	253.4	0.85	0.63	0.79	0.79	16
Flecainide	423	378.3	452.5	318.8	0.23	0.20	0.20	0.20	1448
Halofantrine	374	327.3	395.7	276.7	0.50	0.40	0.50	0.40	172
Haloperidol	327	281.9	345.8	236.2	2.24	1.58	2.00	2.00	3.6
Ibutilide	424	401.8	482.3	337.4	0.18	0.13	0.16	0.16	22
Levofloxacin	325	278.9	342.7	233.8	3.02	2.00	2.51	2.51	30932
Methadone	335	289.8	354.0	242.8	1.51	1.26	1.58	1.26	507
Moxifloxacin	325	278.5	343.2	233.8	2.75	2.51	2.51	2.51	6228
Ondansetron	341	296.3	360.2	247.8	2.75	0.79	1.26	0.79	178.6
Procainamide	328	279.6	346.4	237.1	2.19	2.00	2.00	1.58	35058
Quinidine	519	468.5	581.8	400.0	0.10	0.08	0.08	0.08	2960
Sotalol	319	272.7	336.6	228.9	6.17	3.98	5.01	5.01	18358
Sparfloxacin	324	277.6	342.1	233.3	2.75	2.51	3.16	2.51	1766
Tedisamil	366	322.0	387.1	269.0	0.59	0.40	0.50	0.50	85
Terfenadine	340	294.4	359.2	247.1	1.23	0.79	1.26	0.79	9

Compound	QT _{int} (ms)	APD ₉₀ (ms)			Tx QT	Tx APD			EFTPC (nM)
		ENDO	M	EPI		ENDO	M	EPI	
Terodiline	322	276.4	340.2	231.7	3.80	2.51	3.16	3.16	11.23
Thioridazine	563	539.3	659.3	456.8	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.04	979
Clozapine	316	270.3	334.7	227.4	9.12	7.94	7.94	6.31	70.8
Dasatinib	313	266.6	330.5	224.0	169.82	125.89	158.49	158.49	20.4
Lapatinib	319	272.7	336.6	228.9	5.25	3.98	5.01	5.01	41.8
Nilotinib	377	333.5	399.4	278.7	0.48	0.32	0.40	0.40	60
Ofloxacin	314	267.3	331.3	224.6	36.31	25.12	31.62	31.62	8656
Paliperidone	322	274.4	338.2	230.1	4.07	3.16	3.98	3.98	68.9
Risperidone	317	271.5	335.3	227.8	7.41	5.01	6.31	6.31	6.96
Saquinavir	311	259.9	328.5	223.1	17.78	39.81	39.81	15.85	334
Sunitinib	315	268.4	332.3	225.4	2.95	2.00	2.51	2.51	19
Tolterodine	325	278.9	342.7	233.8	7.24	5.01	6.31	6.31	0.39
Metronidazole	317	271.5	335.3	227.8	2.24	5.01	5.01	2.00	210336
Nelfinavir	316	246.3	331.4	232.8	46.77	31.62	39.81	39.81	60.25
Paroxetine	314	267.2	331.1	224.5	33.11	39.81	39.81	31.62	12.7
Quetiapine	314	267.2	331.3	224.6	1.82	1.58	2.00	1.58	461.9
Ranolazine	330	283.3	348.4	238.4	1.20	0.79	1.26	0.79	2311
Solifenacin	341	295.8	360.0	247.6	15.85	12.59	15.85	15.85	3.47
Voriconazole	314	267.7	331.9	225.2	23.99	25.12	25.12	15.85	5699
Alvimopan	313	266.5	330.5	224.0	42657.95	125892.54	79432.82	79432.82	5.17
Ambrisentan	313	266.5	330.5	224.0	1479.11	1000.00	1258.93	1000.00	75.3
Ceftriaxone	314	266.5	332.7	226.0	11.48	15.85	12.59	7.94	13704
Darifenacin	314	266.9	330.8	224.2	64.57	50.12	63.10	63.10	0.27
Darunavir	314	267.2	331.2	224.4	40.74	31.62	39.81	31.62	862.5
Deferasirox	313	266.5	330.5	223.9	1000.00	1995.26	1584.89	794.33	1403
Desvenlafaxine	315	268.9	332.8	225.9	14.13	10.00	12.59	12.59	3901
Diazepam	313	266.5	330.5	224.0	512.86	1000.00	630.96	501.19	29
Diltiazem	310	258.3	326.9	221.8	38.02	100.00	79.43	39.81	120.6
Doxorubicin	321	275.2	344.4	229.7	19.05	12.59	7.94	15.85	4646
Duloxetine	313	266.6	330.7	224.1	114.82	125.89	100.00	79.43	9.22
Ebastine	313	266.5	330.5	224.0	1148.15	794.33	1000.00	794.33	0.14
Eltrombopag	348	303.3	367.4	253.5	0.89	0.63	0.79	0.79	158.9
Etravirine	313	266.5	330.5	224.0	10471.29	7943.28	10000.00	10000.00	3.38
Everolimus	313	266.5	330.5	224.0	9332.54	7943.28	7943.28	7943.28	8.03
Lamivudine	312	265.0	329.7	223.4	501.19	1584.89	1258.93	794.33	1446
Lamotrigine	326	280.0	345.3	234.7	2.29	2.00	2.00	2.00	19083

Compound	QT _{int} (ms)	APD ₉₀ (ms)			Tx QT	Tx APD			EFTPC (nM)
		ENDO	M	EPI		ENDO	M	EPI	
Linezolid	310	254.8	325.9	221.7	16.22	50.12	39.81	15.85	24856
Loratadine	313	266.5	330.5	224.0	3388.44	3981.07	3981.07	3162.28	0.4
Maraviroc	315	268.1	332.0	225.2	21.38	15.85	19.95	15.85	415
Mibefradil	313	265.9	330.5	224.0	50.12	100.00	79.43	39.81	12
Mitoxantrone	313	266.0	330.1	223.7	831.76	2511.89	1995.26	1258.93	225
Nebivolol	314	266.9	330.8	224.2	70.79	50.12	63.10	63.10	1
Nifedipine	299	236.6	315.7	216.1	1479.11	3981.07	2511.89	1995.26	32.3
Nisoldipine	313	266.5	330.5	223.9	81283.05	251188.64	158489.32	125892.54	0.10
Palonosetron	313	266.5	330.5	224.0	426.58	316.23	398.11	398.11	1.04
Pentobarbital	314	266.4	331.0	224.2	77.62	125.89	50.12	50.12	5171
Phenytoin	312	258.4	328.1	223.1	13.18	31.62	31.62	12.59	3964
Propranolol	313	266.6	330.5	224.0	177.83	158.49	199.53	158.49	10.1
Raltegravir	317	269.1	335.9	226.4	24.55	39.81	12.59	15.85	7000
Ribavirin	315	267.4	332.0	225.3	17.78	25.12	19.95	15.85	15069
Sildenafil	314	266.9	330.8	224.2	70.79	63.10	79.43	63.10	100
Sildenafil	313	266.6	330.5	224.0	158.49	125.89	158.49	158.49	11.2
Sitagliptin	314	266.8	330.9	224.3	69.18	79.43	63.10	50.12	589
S-oxybutynin	313	266.5	330.5	224.0	52480.75	63095.73	63095.73	50118.72	0.05
Tadalafil	313	266.5	330.5	224.0	446.68	316.23	398.11	316.23	50.1
Telbivudine	314	267.4	331.9	224.5	954.99	630.96	316.23	794.33	14731

Figure S3. Tx-APD_{Endo} ROC curves at 0.5, 1 and 2 Hz pacing rates.

Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) Curves of the Tx values obtained in the O'Hara-Rudy cardiac Endo cell model¹ at three pacing rates (blue: 1Hz; orange: 2 Hz; yellow: 0.5 Hz). Optimal Thresholds (Th), True Positive Rates (TPR) and True Negative Rates (TNR) are shown in the legend.

References

1. O'Hara, T.; Virág, L.; Varró, A.; Rudy, Y. Simulation of the Undiseased Human Cardiac Ventricular Action Potential: Model Formulation and Experimental Validation. *PLoS Comput. Biol.* **2011**, 7 (5), e1002061.